

Two subspecies names of *Rhagium inquisitor* (Linnaeus, 1758) from Central Europe and North America (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) are restored

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Abstract. *Rhagium inquisitor lineatum* (Olivier, 1795), **rest. nom.** and *Rh. i. sudeticum* Plavilstshikov, 1936, **rest. nom.** (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) are proposed as valid names.

Introduction

The genus includes several similar taxa from Europe, Asia, Africa and North America. European taxa are still regarded as one species *Rhagium inquisitor*. Many local populations from all over North America were originally described as different species.

Now all American names are paradoxally accepted (Bezark, 2025) as synonyms of the nominative subspecies *Rh. i. inquisitor* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Figs 1-2) described from West Europe. Unfortunately, the adequate taxonomy of American *Rh. inquisitor* needs careful study of local materials, which are not in my disposal. Rather probably many American names could be revalidated at species level, but now I preliminary propose the oldest American name for all - *Rh. i. lineatum* (Olivier, 1795), **rest. nom.** The name was accepted as valid by Podaný (1964) for N. Amerika and Canada: British Columbia, Alberta, Manitoba, Quebec, Ontario, N. Scotland, Oregon, California, Idaho, Arizona, Colorado, New York, Massachusetts, Alaska, New Mexico.

Variability of European populations is poorly investigated. In fact, it is not less than American. Only Far East populations of

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Rhagium sensu Lazarev 2024 were more or less adequately accepted as several species.

Materials and methods

All photographs were taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1-30.5 mm 1:2.8-4.5. The illustrations were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20.

Acronyms of collections:

MD - collection of M.L. Danilevsky (Moscow, Russia);

ML - collection of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow, Russia).

Results

Genus *Rhagium* Fabricius, 1775

Rhagium Fabricius, 1775: 182; 1776: 51; Olivier, 1791: 367; Stephens, 1831: 253; Audinet-Serville, 1835: 205; Westwood, 1839: 41; Curtis, 1839: 750; Blanchard, 1845: 164; Haldeman, 1847: 58; LeConte, 1850b: 319; 1854: 219; 1874: 190; Emmons, 1854: 125; Schiødte, 1865: 205; Chenu, 1870: 330; Redtenbacher, 1874: 428; LeConte & Horn, 1883: 313; Bates, 1885: 277; Leng, 1890: 65; Wickham, 1897a: 88; Blatchley, 1910: 1046, 1048; Schaufuß, 1916: 827; Boppe, 1921: 37; Craighead, 1923: 83; Planet, 1924: 107; Portevin, 1927: 18; Picard, 1929: 66; Winkler, 1929: 1146; Böving & Craighead, 1931: pl. 99 (figs G, H); Arnett, 1962: 857, 877; Chemsak, 1964: 234; 2005: 33, 118; Podaný, 1964: 5; Hansen, 1966: 70; Hatch, 1971: 124; Linsley & Chemsak, 1972: 84; Mamaev & Danilevsky, 1975: 108, 112 (larva); Bílý & Mehl, 1989: 35; Bense, 1995: 41, 111; Monné, 1995: 30; Sama, 2003: 12; Silfverberg, 2004: 76; Tamutis et al., 2011: 316; Sama & Rapuzzi, 2011: 128; Berger, 2012: 81; Švácha & Lawrence, 2014: 153, 156; Haack & al., 2017: 84; Bousquet & al., 2017: 104; Bouchard & al., 2024: 465; Özdikmen, 2024: 2704, 2706 (sensu Lazarev, 2024).

Hargium Leach, 1819: 210, type species: *Cerambyx inquisitor* Linnaeus, 1758.

Allorhagium Kolbe, 1884: 270, type species: *Cerambyx inquisitor* Linnaeus, 1758.

Rhagium (*Allorhagium* Semenov, 1898: 601), unjustified amendment.

Rhagium (*Hargium*), Aurivillius, 1912: 164; Harde, 1966: 19, part.; Kaszab, 1971: 42, part.

Harpium (s. str.) Reitter, 1913: 7, misspelling (unavailable name).

Rhagium (*Hargium* department *Hargium*), Plavilstshikov, 1932: 93.

Rhagium (*Hargium* skupina *Hargium*), Heyrovský, 1955: 76, part.

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Rhagium (*Hargium* sect. *Hargium*), Plavilstshikov, 1915: 34; 1936: 133, 504; Panin & Săvulescu, 1961: 84.

Stenocorus (s. str.), Gressitt, 1951: 54.

Rhagium (*Allorhagium*), Planet, 1924: 109; Portevin, 1927: 19; Gressitt, 1953: 207

Stenocorus, Geoffroy, 1762: 221; Olivier, 1795: (69) 1, part.; Lamarck, 1817: 312; Thomson, 1861: 144, 156; 1864: 144, 409; Lacordaire, 1868: 428; LeConte, 1873: 328; Provancher, 1877: 580, 605; Swaine & Hopping, 1928: 12, 14; Bradley, 1930: 235; Chagnon, 1936: 244; Hopping, 1937: 9; Knull, 1946: 151, 173; Dillon & Dillon, 1961: 618; Chagnon & Robert, 1962: 241, 244.

Rhagium (s. str.), Aurivillius 1912: 161; Planet, 1924: 111; Portevin, 1927: 18; Villiers, 1978: 79; Lobanov & al., 1981: 795; Danilevsky & Miroshnikov, 1985: 123; Bílý & Mehl, 1989: 38; Švácha, 1989: 54 (larva); Pesarini & Sabbadini, 1994: 14; Althoff & Danilevsky, 1997: 9; Vives, 2000: 215; Martynov & Pisarenko, 2004: 47; Bartenev, 2004: 25; 2009: 40; N.Ohbayashi, 2007: 352; Danilevsky & Smetana, 2010: 132; Özdikmen & Turgut, 2010: 967; Danilevsky, 2014: 86; Danilevsky, 2020: 175.

Type species: *Cerambyx inquisitor* Linnaeus, 1758

Prothorax with big lateral protuberances and with a long and wide intercoxal process reaching hind coxal cavities; each elytron with 2-3 distinct carinae; antennae short, surpassing elytral bases; temples shining, much shorter than eyes; slightly protruding laterally; each elytron with two diffused pale belts.

The circumpolar genus includes 9 species.

***Rhagium inquisitor* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Cerambyx inquisitor Linnaeus (= Linné), 1758: 393 - "Europa"; 1761: 190; 1767: 630 - "Europa"; Poda, 1761: 33 "ad Graecium"; Schrank, 1781: 136 - Austria.

Cerambyx nubeculus Bergsträsser, 1778: 26 - "in der Grafschaft Hanau-Münzenberg".

Rhagium inquisitor, Fabricius, 1781: 229 - "Europae truncis arborum"; 1787: 145 - "Germania"; 1793: 304 - "Europae truncis arborum"; Fabricius, 1802: 313 - "Europa"; Schönherr, 1817: 412 - "Europa"; Audinet-Serville, 1835: 206 - "Environs de Paris"; Castelnau, 1840: 500 - "France, Suisse"; Küster, 1848: 84 - "Vom nördlichen Europa durch die ganze Mitte bis Frankreich und Oberitalien"; Saalas, 1936: 70 - "Europa, Sibirien, Japan"; Reymond, 1953: 203 - "Maroc (Moyen-Atlas), Algérie (Djurdjura et Babor)"; Duffy, 1960: 74 - "Europe, Scotland, Siberia, North Africa, Japan"; Mulsant, 1863: 454, part.; Lindeman, 1871: 205, part.; Ganglbauer, 1882a: 718; 1882b: 40; Köenig, 1899: 393; Winkler, 1929: 1147, part.; Hayashi, 1960: 3; 1963: 129; Ilinsky, 1962: 301, larva; Krivolutskaya, 1965: 62; Plavilstshikov,

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- 1965: 398; Paulus, 1969: 5, larva; Alekseev & Lurye 1970: 651, larva; Mamaev & Danilevsky, 1975: 114, larva; Tsherepanov, 1979: 77 part., larva, biology; Kadyrbekov & Tleppaeva, 1997: 41 - Almaty Nature Reserve; Danilevsky, 1982: 814, key to larvae of the genus; Krivosheina & Kompantsev, 1984: 169, biology; Sama, 1988: 7; Adlbauer, 1992: 489 - Turkey; Bense, 1995: 111; Pesarini & Sabbadini, 1995: 68 - "Europa, Africa settentrionale, Asia temperata, Nordamerica"; Grosso-Silva, 2000: 40 - "Portugal: Manteigas"; Warzee & Drumont, 2004: 49 - "Belgique"; Migliaccio & al., 2004: 140 - "Vitoshka Mountain, Bulgaria"; Micas, 2005: 148 - "vallon de la Moulière (Alpes-de-Haute-Provence)"; Rapuzzi & Sama, 2006: 160 - "Sicilia: Etna"; Brin & al., 2006: 60 - "vallée du Marcadau (Hautes-Pyrénées)"; Simon, 2007: 155 - "Domaine de Rochebois à Vitrac (Dordogne)"; Ehnström & Holmer, 2007: 22, 32, 55, 110 - Sweden, Denmark, Norway, Finland; Rousset, 2007: 46 - "forêt de Maubert, entre Saint-Amandin, Condat et Trémouille (Cantal)"; Dodelin & Sauvagère, 2009: 3 - "Haute-Normandie"; Berger & al., 2010: 21 - "Grèce : province de Ionnina, 7 km au nord de Konitsa"; Tamutis & al., 2011: 316 - Litva; Lindhe & al., 2011: 278, 279 - "Sweden"; Pacini, 2011: 15 - "Uzhgorod, the Carpathians, Ukraine"; Berger, 2012: 82; Dobrosavljević & Mihajlović, 2014: 24 - "Serbia"; Švácha & Lawrence, 2014, biology; Plewa & al., 2014: 128 - "Romania"; Lim & al., 2014: 131 - "Korea"; Choi & al., 2016: 239 - "South Korea"; Troukens & al., 2017: 14 - "omgeving van Brussel"; Żurawlew & Melke, 2018: 84 - "Poland: Pleszew District (Wielkopolska-Kujawy Lowland)"; Vitali, 2018: 73 - "Luxembourg"; Yalçın & al., 2020: 6 - "Northwest Turkey"; Dovhaniuk & Zamoroka, 2020: 134 - Ukraine (Ternopil Region): National Park "Kremenetski Hory"; Barševskis & al., 2021: 136 - "Latvia: Kinkausku forest, Celminiki"; Ruchin & et al., 2022: 17 - Central European Russia; Zamoroka, 2022: 55 - Ukraine; Saikina & al., 2022: 798 - Russia: Omsk Region; Trócoli & al., 2023: 243 - "España (Barcelona, Catalunya): Moianès"; Volovnik, 2024: 44 - "Southern Ukraine: Zaporizhia Oblast".
- Rhagium indagator* Fabricius, 1787: 145 - "Germania"; Gebler, 1830: 189 - Altay; 1848: 410 - "um Salair, im kusnezsk."; Mulsant, 1839: 227 - France; 1863: 456, part.; Küster, 1848: 85 - "Im nördlichen und mittleren Europa bis zum gemäßigten Süden häufig"; Motschulsky, 1859: 493 - "environs du fl. Amour, depuis la Schilka jusqu'à Nikolaëvsk"; 1860a: 310 - "Songarie"; 1860b: 149 - "Dans toute la Sibérie"; Lindeman, 1871: 205, part.
- Rhagium minutum* Fabricius, 1787: 146 - Germany: "Kiliae".
- Cerambyx (Rhagium) indagator*, Gmelin, 1790: 1845 - "Germania".
- Cerambyx (Rhagium) exilis* Gmelin, 1790: 1844.
- Cerambyx (Rhagium) inquisitor*, Gmelin, 1790: 1845 - "Europae truncis arborum"
- Stenocorus inquisitor*, Olivier, 1795: (69) 9; Lamarck, 1801: 235; 1817: 313; Gemminger, 1872: 2855; Schneider & Leder, 1879: 320 - "Suram" (= *indagator* F.); Baudi di Selve, 1889: 185 - Piemonte.
- Stenocorus indagator*, Olivier, 1795: (69) 12, part.
- Stenocorus minutus*, Olivier, 1795: (69) 15, part. - "en Allemagne".

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- Leptura inquisitor*, Latreille, 1804: 307 - "toute l'Europe".
- Stenocorus cephalotes minor* Voet, 1806: 29, nomen nudum.
- Rhagium fortipes* Reitter, 1898: 357 - Turkey: Hatay.
- Allorhagium inquisitor*, Matsumura, 1911: 134, part. - "Japan, Amur, Europa".
- Rhagium (Hargium) inquisitor*, Aurivillius, 1912: 164 - "Europa, Sibirien, Japan; Schaufuß", 1916: 828 - "Fernere paläarktische Arten"; Villiers, 1946: 39 - "Algérie"; Heyrovský, 1955: 79; Panin & Sävulescu, 1961: 84; Kaszab, 1971: 44.
- Harpium* (s. str.) *inquisitor*, Reitter, 1913: 7.
- Rhagium Iberonis* Ericson, 1916: 240 - "Ibero".
- Rhagium (Allorhagium) inquisitor*, Peyerimhoff, 1919: 209 - "Babor, Djurdjura".
- Rhagium* (s. str.) *inquisitor*, Portevin, 1927: 19 - France; Villiers, 1978: 80; Lobanov & al., 1981: 795; Danilevsky & Miroschnikov, 1985: 125; Švácha, 1989: 54, 58, part., larva; Althoff & Danilevsky, 1997: 9; Vincent, 1998: 24 - "Ile de France"; Tozlu & al., 2002: 62 - Turkey; Sama, 2002: 12; Bartenev, 2004: 25, part.; 2009: 40, part.; Denux, 2005: 229, 236 - "Parc naturel régional du Perche (Orne & Eure-et-Loir)"; Berger & Peslier, 2014: 570 - "toute la France"; Facon, 2016: 8 - "France: Montreuillois"; Cartier & Cartier, 2016: 229 - "Vienne: Vouillé"; Klausnitzer & al., 2016: 337 - "Mitteleuropa"; Stolbov & al., 2019: 200 - Russia (Tyumenskaya Oblast); Alekseev & Maryutin, 2019: 6 - Russia (Kalouga); Özdikmen 2021a: 443 - Turkey; 2021b: 511 - Turkey; Bunalski & al., 2022: 12 - Western Poland.
- Rhagium (Hargium) inquisitor*, Plavilshnikov, 1932: 94.
- Rhagium (Hargium) inquisitor*, Plavilshnikov, 1936: 141, 504, part.
- Rhagium (Hargium) inquisitor*, G. Müller, 1949: 42.
- Rhagium (Hargium) inquisitor fortipes*, Podaný, 1964: 20 - "Akbés, Syrien", part.
- Rhagium inquisitor*, Kadyrbekov & al., 1996: 86, misspelling - Zailiysky Alatau on the Shrenk spruce (Medeo).
- Rhagium (Megarhagium) inquisitor*, Reisdorf & al., 2015: 155 - "Marais de Montabé (Essonne)".
- Rhagium* (s.str.) *inquisitor*, Şabanoğlu, 2020: 199, misspelling - "Turkey: Rize".

Type locality. "Europa" and rather probably Sweden (Tavakilian & Chevillotte, 2025).

Body moderately dark with distinct elytral carinae strongly developed; general body color from rather pale to nearly black; body length: 9.5-20.0 mm.

Distribution. North Asia (without Central Asia and Palestine), North America. North Africa and about whole Europe.

Bionomy. Larvae develop under the dead bark of various coniferous trees: *Pinus*, *Picea*, *Abies*, *Cedrus*, *Larix*, etc., but development on deciduous trees has also been frequently noted: *Betula* (especially in

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Siberia), *Populus*, *Quercus*, *Fagus*; in Sweden *Alnus* is often infested (Palm, 1959); *Betula* has been noted to be populated in the Kostroma region (Krivosheina & Kompantsev, 1984). Pupation under the bark occurs at the end of summer; the imago overwinters. Adult beetles are active in spring and early summer, occasionally visiting flowers. Generation is 2 years.

***Rhagium inquisitor lineatum* (Olivier, 1795), rest. nom.**

Stenocorus lineatus Olivier, 1795: 13 - "Amérique"; Provancher, 1877: 605 - "Canada"; Doane & al., 1936: 170; Chagnon, 1936: 244 - "Province de Québec"; Kimmey & Furniss, 1943: 262, biology; Craighead, 1950: 262, biology - "Throughout United States"; Becker, 1955: 164, biology - "Massachusetts"; Clark, 1956: 41 - "near Terrace, British Columbia"; Townes & Townes, 1960: 140 - "America, north of Mexico"; Chagnon & Robert, 1962: 244 - "Québec".

Rhagium lineatum, Schönherr, 1817: 414 - "America"; Audinet-Serville, 1835: 207 - "Amérique du Nord"; Harris, 1838: 95 - "in Massachusetts"; 1841: 93 - "Massachusetts"; Haldeman, 1847: 58 - United States; LeConte, 1850a: 235; 1850b: 319 - "Maine to Chihuahua"; 1879: 505 - Alpine Rocky Mountain Regions; Melshimer, 1853: 112 - United States; Emmons, 1854: 126 - New York; Glover, 1869: 104, biology; Dimmock, 1871: 15; Packard, 1872: 501, biology; Fuller, 1875: 97, biology - "New Jersey"; Moody, 1875: 96, biology - "Massachusetts"; Planchard, 1875: 96, biology - "Massachusetts"; Andrews, 1875: 80 - "Maryland"; Riley, 1880: 239, biology; Harrington, 1881: 33; Packard, 1881: 162, 226, 236, biology; Riley, 1883: 259, biology; Bates, 1885: 277 - North America. Mexico, Morelia, Las Vigas; Schwarz, 1886a: 29, biology; 1886b, 27, biology; Horn, 1886: 138; Mann, 1886: 27; Holland, 1888: 91 - "British Columbia"; Riley & Howard, 1889: 190, biology; Townsend, 1889: 233 - "the Lower peninsula of Michigan"; 1895: 48 - "New Mexico"; Packard, 1890: 704, 830, 862, biology; Hopkins, 1893: 195, biology; 1899: 439, biology; 1904: 37, biology - "the Louisiana Purchase Exposition St. Louis, Mo."; Chittenden, 1893: 248, biology; Hanham, 1894: 352 - "Quebec"; Slosson, 1894 - "Mount Washington (New Hampshire)"; 1896: 263 - "in alpine region of Mt. Washington"; Chittenden, 1895: 419; Keen, 1895: 219 - "British Columbia"; Laurent, 1895: 323 - "Maine"; Evans, 1895: 173 - "Ontario"; Beutenmüller, 1896: 77 - North America; Wickham, 1897b: 170 - Canada: "Ontario and Quebec"; Warren, 1899: 296 - "Tioga County, Pennsylvania"; Smith, 1900: 291 - "in New Jersey"; 1910: 330 - "New Jersey"; Fall, 1901: 148 - "southern California"; Ulke, 1903: 26, 50 - "District of Columbia"; Felt, 1903: 492, biology - "Albany, Lansingburgh"; Felt, 1906: 335, 339, 349, 366, biology; Wenzel, 1905: 159 - "New Jersey"; Fall & Cockerell, 1907: 193 - "New Mexico"; Morris, 1908: 443, biology; 1916:19 - "Port Hope District"; Blatchley, 1910: 1048 - "in Indiana"; Fisher & Kirk, 1912: 312 - "Harrisburg, Pennsylvania"; Engelhardt, 1912: 221 -

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“Long Island”; Chagnon, 1917: 233 - “Province of Quebec”; Woodruff, 1917: 85 - Lakehurst, New Jersey; 1939: 86 - “Laurentide Provincial Park, Montmorency County, Québec”; Hess, 1917: 64, 67, 68, larva; 1920: 367, biology; Nicolay, 1917: 94 - “Maine”; 1919: 68, biology - “Long Island”; Garnett, 1918: 212 - “California”; Britton, 1920: 267 - “Connecticut”; Craighead, 1923: 88, larva; Munding, 1924: 316 - “Cranberry Lake region, New York”; Essig, 1926: 451 - “New Mexico, Colorado, California, Nevada, Oregon, Washington, British Columbia, Alaska and all the Western States”; Kirk & Knoll, 1926: 23 - “Pennsylvania”; Fletcher, 1926: 143 - “Lloyd-Cornell Reservation”; Hardy, 1926: 4 - “Vancouver Island”; 1927: C24, biology; 1955: B50 - “Vancouver Island, British Columbia”; Hardy & Preece, 1926: 35 - “from the southern portion of Vancouver Island, B.C.”; Procter, 1927: 111 - “Mount Desert Region”; 1946: 177, biology; Tanner, 1927: 33; 1928: 277 - “Zion National Park, Utah”; Leonard, 1928: 437 - “Staten Island, Long Island”; Keen, 1929: 64 - California; Pack, 1930: 219 - “Utah”; Beaulne, 1932: 198 - “Canada”; Ingles, 1933: 59, biology; Wolcott & Montgomery, 1933: 155, biology; Easterling, 1934: 131, 135, 140 - “in Southeastern Ohio”; Mank, 1934: 80 - “Glacier Park, Montana”; DeLeon, 1934: 57; Herrick, 1935: 251; Knowlton & Thatcher, 1936: 279; Lange, 1937: 173 - “California”; Brimley, 1938: 211 - “North Carolina”; Savely, 1939: 333, biology; Parmelee, 1941: 377 - “Michigan”; Löding, 1945: 116 - “Alabama”; Jaques, 1951: 254; Ross, 1967: 24, biology - “British Columbia”; 1968: 11, biology - “British Columbia”.

Hargium lineatum, Kirby, 1837: 178 - “Latitude 54°, Massachusets”.

Rhagium investigator, Mannerheim, 1852: 367 - “insula Sithka”

Rhagium minutum, Chevrolat, 1851: 664 - “Etats-Unis”.

Rhagium inquisitor, Maeklin, 1857: 186 - “Sithka”; Fauvel, 1889: 150, part. - “Amérique du Nord jusqu'au Mexique. Europe, Sibérie, Japon”; Hamilton, 1894a: 31 - “Alaska”; 1894b: 396, part. - North America, northern Asia and Europe; 1895: 338 - “southwestern Pennsylvania”; Blackwelder, 1946: 573, part. - “[Old World]”; Gardiner, 1957: 251, larva - “Ontario”; Tyson, 1966: 206 - “California”; Gardiner, 1966: 209; 1970: 286, biology - “Ontario, Quebec”; Linsley & Chemsak, 1972: 85 - “Holarctic, boreal in North America”; Perry, 1975: 59 - “Virginia”; Kirk & Balsbaugh, 1975: 98 - “South Dakota”; Gosling & Gosling, 1976: 5 - Michigan; Laliberté & al., 1977: 97, biology - “Québec”; Skiles, 1978: 14 - “Los Angeles County, California”; Gosling, 1986: 157 - “northern Michigan”; Drouin, 1991: 175 - “Québec”; Chemsak & al., 1992: 100 - “borNAmer, México”; MacRae, 1993: 238 - Missouri; Pesarini & Sabbadini, 1995: 68, part. - “Europa, Africa settentrionale, Asia temperata, Nordamerica”; Monné, 1995: 31 - “Holarctic, boreal in North America”; Noguera & Chemsak, 1996: 403 - “Michoacán”; Linsley & Chemsak, 1997: 428; Peck & Thomas, 1998: 120 - Florida; Allison & al., 2000: 4 - North America; Vlasák & Vlasakova, 2002: 207 - “Massachusetts”; Chemsak, 2005: 119 - “boreal in North America”; Costello & al., 2013: 151 - USA (South Dakota): Black Hills; Bousquet & al., 2017: 104- “from the Alexander Archipelago in

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- southeastern Alaska to Newfoundland, as far north as central Yukon Territory”; Haack, 2020: 76 - “Michigan (Drummond Island): Chippewa County”; Chapman & al., 2023: 64 - USA (Kentucky).
- Hargium [Rhagium] lineatum*, Bethune, 1872: 96 “in Lat. 54°, in the province of Massachusetts.”.
- Rhagium lineatus*, Leng, 1890: 65.
- Rhagium (Allorhagium) inquisitor*, Bedel, 1906: 291, part. - “djabal Babor. Europe, Asie jusqu'au Japon, Amérique jusqu'au Mexique”; Planet, 1924: 109, part. - “Europe, Asie et Amérique du Nord”.
- Rhagium (Hargium) inquisitor* var. *lineatum*, Aurivillius, 1912: 165 - “Nordamerika”; Boppe, 1921: 38 - “Amérique septentrionale”.
- Rhagium (Hargium) californicum* Casey, 1913: 195 - “California (Sacramento Co.)”; Lingafelter & al., 2014: 35, 369, lectotype.
- Rhagium (Hargium) crassipes* Casey, 1913: 195 - “Massachusetts (Medford)”; Lingafelter & al., 2014: 47, holotype.
- Rhagium (Hargium) parvicorne* Casey, 1913: 195 - “Massachusetts (Maiden)”; Lingafelter & al., 2014: 296, holotype.
- Rhagium (Hargium) boreale* Casey, 1913: 195 - “Wisconsin (Bayfield), - Wickham”; Lingafelter & al., 2014: 31, holotype.
- Rhagium (Hargium) cariniventre* Casey, 1913: 196 - “Massachusetts and Pennsylvania”; Podaný, 1964: 33; Lingafelter & al., 2014: 37, 369, lectotype.
- Rhagium (Hargium) thoracicum* Casey, 1913: 196 - “New Mexico”; Lingafelter & al., 2014: 333, holotype.
- Rhagium (Hargium) lineatum*, Casey, 1913: 196 - “North-eastern States”; Podaný, 1964: 23.
- Rhagium (Hargium) montanum* Casey, 1913: 197 - “Colorado (Fraser 8000 feet and in Boulder Co.) and New Mexico (Las Vegas)”; Podaný, 1964: 31; Lingafelter & al., 2014: 101, 369, lectotype.
- Rhagium (Hargium) mexicanum* Casey, 1913: 197 - “Mexico (Guerrero)”; Blackwelder, 1946: 573 - “México”; Podaný, 1964: 35; Lingafelter & al., 2014: 98, 369, lectotype.
- Rhagium (Hargium) canadense* Podaný, 1964: 30 - “Marming Par, BC, 4000””; Ulmen & al., 2010: 12
- Rhagium (Hargium) americanum* Podaný, 1964: 32 - “N. Amer.”
- Rhagium (Hargium) quadricostatum* Podaný, 1964: 34 - “Fort Smith, NWT”.
- Stenocorus lineatum*, Canova, 1936: 131 - “Oregon”; Leech, 1947: 108 - “British Columbia”.
- Stenocorus inquisitor*, Hopping, 1937: 9 - “...America North of Mexico”; Knull, 1946: 174 - “Ohio”; Fattig, 1947: 13 - “Georgia” (U.S. state); Hardy, 1948: 32 - “Manning Park, British Columbia”; Knowlton & Wood, 1950: 11 - “Utah”; Howden & Vogt, 1951: 591 - “Coastal Plain of Maryland”; Beal & al., 1952: 110, biology - “Piedmont Plateau of North Carolina”; Thomas, 1955: 340, biology; Dillon & Dillon, 1961: 618 - North America; Wilson, 1971: 61, biology - “New England”; Hatch, 1971: 138 - “Pacific Northwest”.
- Rhagium inquisitor* var. *lineatum*, Blackwelder, 1946: 573 (= *investigator* Mannh.) - “México, U. S. A.”; Duffy, 1960: 74 - Mexico, U.S.A., Canada.

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- Rhagium (Hargium) inquisitor*, Duffy, 1953: 127, larva - imported from North America.
Stenocorus inquisitor lineatus, Baker, 1972: 206, biology.
Rhagium papayanum Podaný, 1978: 4 - “Mexique”; Zaragoza-Caballero & Pérez-Hernández, 2017: 38 - “Mexico: Estado de México, Río Frío, Papayo”.
- Rhagium mexicanum nigra* Podaný, 1978: 4 - “Mexique”.
- Rhagium* (s. str.) *inquisitor*, Villiers, 1978: 80, part. - “France, Europe, Afrique du Nord, Sibérie occidentale. Amerique du Nord, Caucase, Asie mineure”; Vives, 2000: 216, part. - “paleártica y Norteamérica”; 2001: 115, part. - “paleártica, alcanza la zona boreal norteamericana”.
- Rhagium inquisitor inquisitor*, Monné & Giesbert, 1994: 169 - “Holarctic: NAmer (boreal regions)”; Schiefer, 1998: 121 - “Mississippi”; Heffern, 1998: 9, part. - “AK, AL, AZ, CA, CO, CT, FL, GA, ID, IN, MA, MD, ME, MI, MS, MT, NC, NJ, NM, NY, OH, OK, OR, PA, SC, SD, TX, UT, WA, WI, AB, BC, MB, NB, NF, NT, ON, PQ, SK, YK Mexico, Europe, Asia”; Holt, 2013: 245 - “Alabama”; Klingeman & al., 2017: 296 - “Tennessee”; Rice & al., 2017: 670 - “Idaho”; Lagos Ordoñez & Nápoles, 2024: 43 - “Canadá, EUA, México (Guerrero, México, Michoacán, Puebla)”; Martínez-Hernández & al., 2024: 189 - “Mexico (Oaxaca): Oaxaca, Santiago Xiacui”.
- Rhagium canadense*, Ulmen & al., 2010: 12.

Type locality. Northern America.

Temples narrower than eyes, smooth and shining; antennae thick and short; slightly surpassing elytral bases; prothorax wide, elytra with variable sculpture and color strongly carinated; abdomen often partly yellow; body length: 16.0-20.0 mm.

Distribution. About whole territory of North America, from Mexico to Alaska and Canada.

Bionomy. Larvae develop under the bark of coniferous trees (*Picea*, *Pinus*, *Larix*, *Tsuga*, *Pseudotsuga* and others); the generation lasts 2 years. Imagoes active from February to July

***Rhagium inquisitor sudeticum* Plavilstshikov, 1936, rest. nom.**

Figs 3-4

Rhagium inquisitor inquisitor var. *sudetica* Plavilstshikov, 1915: 46 [unavailable name] - “Monts Sudètes”.

Rhagium inquisitor var. *sudeticum* Plavilstshikov, 1936: 143, 504.

Rhagium inquisitor var. *sudetica*, Danilevsky, 2009: 690, type material is not found.

Type locality. Sudeten Mountains or Sudetes.

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According to the original description, antennae much shorter and thinner, than in the nominative subspecies; prothorax longer and narrower; elytra narrower at shoulders, with poorly developed carinae, without wrinkles or with poor wrinkles, with very poor punctation, pale-yellow or ash-grey color; anterior elytral belt absent or hardly pronounced; post middle elytral belt distinct; body length 10.0-12.0 mm.

Material. 1 male, 1 female, Italy, Romagna, 15.8.1975 - MD; 5 males, 3 females, Italy, Veneto, Treviso, Vittorio Veneto, Crodarossa, 14-31.5.1983, L. Costelo leg. - ML; 1 male, Croatia, 26.6.1981 - MD; 2 males, 1 female, Germany, Pfalz, Daun, 12.1975, Schimmel leg. - MD; 2 males, Bulgaria, Pirin, 2.7.1987, 11.8.1987, V. Sakalyan leg. - MD; 1 female, Bulgaria, Sofia, 10.6.2007, T. Ljubomirov leg. - MD.

Distribution. I don't know the type specimens (are not available in Plavilstshikov's collection), but several my series totally agree with the original description: Croatia, Italy, Bulgaria, Germany.

Bionomy. Larvae usually develop under the bark of coniferous trees (*Picea*, *Pinuss*, *Abie*, *Larix*), but sometimes in deciduous trees (*Betula*); the generation lasts 2 years. Imagoes active from April to June.

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Figs 1-2. *Rhagium inquisitor inquisitor* (Linnaeus, 1758). 1. male, Russia, Moscow Region, Udelnaya, 3.4.2010, M. Danilevsky leg.; 2. female, Kazakhstan, 15 km S Almaty, Butakovka, 1600 m, 1.6.2002, M. Danilevsky leg.

Figs 3-4. *Rhagium inquisitor sudeticum* Plavilstshikov, 1936, **rest. nom.**: 3. male, Italy, Romagna, 15.8.1975; 4. female with the same label.

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REFERENCES

- Adlbauer K. 1992. Zur Faunistik und Taxonomie der Bockkäferfauna der Türkei II (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). - Entomofauna, Zeitschrift für Entomologie. 13 (30): 485-509.
- Alekseev A.V. & Lurye M.A. 1970. Practical identification guide to the larvae of longhorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) living on Norway spruce in the European part of the USSR. - Entomological Review. 49 (3): 650-655. [in Russian]
- Alekseev S.K. & Maryutin V.G. 2019. Longhorn Beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of the Federal Natural Monument «Kaluga City Forest». - Proceedings of the Mordovia State Nature Reserve. 23: 3-30. [in Russian]
- Allison J.D., McIntosh R.L., Borden J.H. & Humble L.M. 2000. A new parasitoid (Diptera: Tachinidae) of *Acanthocinus princeps* (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) in North America. - Journal of the Entomological Society of British Columbia. 97: 3-5.
- Althoff J. & Danilevsky M.L. 1997. A check-list of Longicorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycoidea) of Europe. Slovensko Entomolosko Društvo Stefana Michielija. Ljubljana. 64 pp.
- Andrews W.V. 1875. Correspondence. "Have you ever seen a Rhagium?" - The Canadian Entomologist. 7 (4): 76-80.
- Arnett R.H.J. 1962. The Beetles of the United States (A manual for identification). Washington, Catholic University of America Press. 103 (20): xi + 1112 pp.
- Audinet-Serville J.-G. 1835. Nouvelle classification de la famille des longicornes (Suite et fin.). - Annales de la Société Entomologique de France. (1) 4: 197-228.
- Aurivillius C. 1912: Cerambycidae: Cerambycinae. Pars 39. - In: Schenkling S. (ed.): Coleopterorum Catalogus. Volumen 22. Cerambycidae I. Berlin: Junk, 108 + 574 pp
- Baker W.L. 1972. Eastern Forest Insects. - USDA Forest Service Miscellaneous Publications, Washington D.C. 1175: 1-642.
- Barševskis A., Semenyak A., Borodin O., Barševska Z., Borodina O., Lecka K. & Volinko N. 2021. Faunistic records of the beetles (Insecta: Coleoptera) in Latvia. 6. - Baltic Journal of Coleopterology. 21 (2): 127-136.
- Bartenev A.F. 2004. A review of the long-horned beetles species (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of the fauna of Ukraine. - Izvestiya Kharkovskogo Entomologicheskogo Obshestva [The Kharkov Entomological Society Gazette], 2003 (2004), 11 (1-2): 24-43. [in Russian]
- Bartenev A.F. 2009. Longicorn-beetles of Left-Bank Ukraine and Crimea. Kharkov: Kharkov National University. 405pp. [in Russian]
- Bates H.W. 1885. Supplement to Longicornia. - Biologia Centrali-Americana, Insecta, Coleoptera. 5: 249-436, pls. XVII-XXIV.
- Baudi di Selve [Baudi] F. 1889. Catalogo dei Coleotteri del Piemonte. - Annali dell'Accademia Agraria di Torino. 32: 1-226.
- Beal J.A., Haliburton W. & Knight F.B. 1952. Forest insects of the southeast: with special reference to species occurring in the Piedmont Plateau of North Carolina. - Bulletin of the Duke University School of Forestry. 14: 3-168.

M.A. Lazarev

- Beaulne J.T. 1932. Longicornes nuisibles aux végétaux ligneux du Canada. - *Le Naturaliste Canadien*. 59 (10): 196-203.
- Becker W.B. 1955. Tests with BHC emulsion sprays to keep boring insects out of pine logs in Massachusetts. - *Journal of Economic Entomology*. 48 (2): 163-167.
- Bedel L.E.M. 1906. Séance du 27 décembre 1905. Communications. Indication de quelques genres de Coléoptères européens retrouvés récemment en Barbarie. - *Bulletin de la Société Entomologique de France*. 20 (1905): 289-291.
- Bense U. 1995. Longhorn Beetles. Illustrated Key to the Cerambycidae and Vesperidae of Europe. Weikersheim: Margraf. 512 pp.
- Berger P. 2012. Coléoptères Cerambycidae de la faune de France Continentale et de Corse. Actualisation de l'ouvrage d'André Villiers, 1978. Supplément au Tome XXI R.A.R.E. 664 pp.
- Berger P., Kakiopoulos G., Brustel H. & Minetti R. 2010. Contribution à la connaissance des Cérambycides (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) de Grèce: 5ème note. - *Bioscosme Mésogéen*. 27 (1): 17-26.
- Berger P. & Peslier S. 2014. Cerambycidae Latreille, 1802. - In: Marc Tronquet. Catalogue des Coléoptères de France. Association Roussillonnaise d'Entomologie. Supplément au Tome XXIII - RARE. 1052 pp.
- Bergsträsser J.A.B. 1778. Nomenclatur und Beschreibung der Insecten in der Grafschaft Hanau-Münzenberg, wie auch der Wetterau und der angrenzenden Nachbarschaft dies- und jenseits des Mains. 1. Hanau. 88 pp., 14 pls.
- Beutenmüller W. 1896. Food habits of North America Cerambycidae. - *Journal of the New York Entomological Society*. 4: 73-81.
- Bethune C.J.S. 1872. Insects of the northern parts of British America. From Kirby's Fauna Boreali-Americana: Insecta. - *The Canadian Entomologist*. 4 (5): 93-96.
- Bílý S. & Mehl O. 1989. Longhorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of Fennoscandia and Denmark. Fauna Entomologica Scandinavica. 22. Leiden: E. J. Brill. 203 pp.
- Blanchard C.É. 1845. Histoire des Insectes, traitant de leurs moeurs et de leurs métamorphoses en général, et comprenant une nouvelle classification fondée sur leurs rapports naturels. Paris, Didot Frères. 2: 1-524.
- Blackwelder R.E. 1946. Checklist of the coleopterous insects of Mexico, Central America, the West Indies and South America. Part 4. - *Bulletin of the United States National Museum*, Washington D.C. 185 (4): 551-763.
- Blatchley W.S. 1910. An Illustrated Descriptive Catalogue of the Coleoptera or Beetles (exclusive of the Rhynchophora) Known to Occur in Indiana - With Bibliography and Descriptions of New Species. - *Bulletin of the Indiana Department of Geological and Natural Resources*. 1: 1-1386, 595 figs.
- Boppe P.L. 1921. Genera Insectorum. Coleoptera Longicornia fam. Cerambycidae: subfam. Disteniinae-Lepturinae. Bruxelles, P. Wytzman. 178: 1-119, 8 pls.
- Bouchard P., Bousquet Y., Davies A.E. & Cai C. 2024. On the nomenclatural status of type genera in Coleoptera (Insecta). - *ZooKeys*. 1194: 1-981.
- Bousquet Y., Laplante S., Hammond H.E.J. & Langor D.W. 2017. Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) of Canada and Alaska: identification guide with nomenclatural, taxonomic, distributional, host-plant, and ecological data.

M.A. Lazarev

- Nakladatelstvi Jan Farkac, Prague: 1-300, 46 pls.
- Böving A.G. & Craighead F.C. 1931. An illustrated synopsis of the principal larval forms of the order Coleoptera. - *Entomologica Americana* (N. S.). 11 (1) (1930): 1-351.
- Bradley J.C. 1930. A manual of the genera of beetles of America north of Mexico. Ithaca, N.Y., Daw, Illston & Co. 360 pp.
- Brimley C.S. 1938. The insects of North Carolina, Being a List of the Insects of North Carolina and Their Close Relatives. - Raleigh. North Carolina Department of Agriculture, Division Entomology. 560 pp.
- Brin A., Brustel H. & Valladares L. 2006. Contribution à la connaissance des Coleoptères saproxyliques de la vallée du Marcadau (Hautes-Pyrénées). - *Bulletin de la Société Linnéenne de Bordeaux*. 140 (N.S.) 34 (1): 55-64.
- Britton W.E. 1920. Check-list of the insects of Connecticut. - *Connecticut State Geological and Natural History Survey Bulletin*. 31: 1-397.
- Bunalski M. Konwerski S. & Przewoźny M. 2022. Część 24. Cerambycidae: Lepturinae [Contributions to the knowledge of beetles distribution in Western Poland. Part 24. Cerambycidae: Lepturinae]. - *Wiadomości Entomologiczne*. 41 (4): 7-17.
- Canova M.F. 1936. An annotated list of the Lepturini of Oregon. - *The Pan-Pacific Entomologist*. 12 (3): 126-132.
- Cartier J.-C. & Cartier G. 2016. Contribution à l'étude de l'entomofaune de la Vienne. Les Cerambycidae de la forêt de Vouillé-Saint-Hilaire (Coleoptera Cerambycidae). - *L'Entomologiste*. 72 (4): 221-234.
- Casey T. L. 1913. II - Further Studies among the American Longicornia, pp.193-388. - In: Casey T. L. *Memoirs on the Coleoptera*, Lancaster: The New Era Printing Company. 4: 1-400.
- Chagnon G. 1917. A preliminary List of the Insects of the Province of Quebec. Part III. Coleoptera. - In: 9th Annual Report of the Quebec Society for the Protection of Plants. (supplement): 161-277.
- Chagnon G. 1936. Contribution à l'étude de Coléoptères de la Province de Québec. Famille XLI. Cérambycides. - *Le Naturaliste Canadien, Québec*. 63 (4): 193-256.
- Chagnon G. 1939. A preliminary list of the insects collected in the Laurentide Provincial Park, Montmorency County, Québec. - In: 70th Annual Report of the Entomological Society of the Province of Ontario: 83-87.
- Chagnon G. & Robert A. 1962. Principaux Coléoptères de la province de Québec. Les Presses de l'Université de Montréal. 440 pp.
- Chapman E.G., Richards A.B., & Dupuis J.R. 2023. The longhorn beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of Kentucky with notes on larval hosts, adult nectar use, and semiochemical attraction. - *Zootaxa*. 5229 (1): 1-89.
- Chemsak J.A. 1964. Type Species of Generic Names Applied to North American Lepturinae (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). - *The Pan-Pacific Entomologist*. 40 (4): 231-237.
- Chemsak J.A. 2005. Illustrated Revision of the Cerambycidae of North America. Volume II Lepturinae. Wolfsgarden Press, Chino, CA: i-xv + 1-446, 27 pls.
- Chemsak J.A., Linsley E.G. & Noguera F.A. 1992. II. Los Cerambycidae y

M.A. Lazarev

- Disteniidae de Norteamérica, Centroamérica y las Indias Occidentales (Coleoptera). Instituto de Biología, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México. Listados Faunísticos de México. 204 pp.
- Chenu J.C. 1870. Encyclopédie d'Histoire Naturelle ou Traité Complet de cette Science d'après les travaux des naturalistes les plus éminents de tous les pays et de toutes les époques: Buffon, Daubenton, Lacépède, G. Cuvier, F. Cuvier, Geoffroy Saint-Hilaire, Latreille, de Jussieu, Brongniart, etc., etc. Ouvrage résumant les observations des auteurs anciens et comprenant toutes les découvertes modernes jusqu'à nos jours. Coléoptères buprestiens, scarabéiens, piméliens, curculioniens, scolytiens, chrysoméliens, etc... Coléoptères. Paris, Marescq & Compagnie 3: vi + 1-360, 296 figs, 48 pls.
- Chevrolat L.A.A. 1851. Note sur les longicornes de la collection de Banks, la plupart types de Fabricius, rapportés aux genres actuels. - Annales de la Société Entomologique de France. (2) 9: 657-664.
- Chittenden F.H. 1893. Observations of some Hymenopterous parasites of Coleoptera. - USDA Insect Life, Washington D.C. 5 (4): 247-251.
- Chittenden F.H. 1895. Some changes in nomenclature. - USDA Insect Life, Washington D.C. 7 (5): 418-419.
- Choi J.-K., Kolarov J., Jeong J.-C. & Lee J.-W. 2016. A taxonomic review of the genus *Dolichomitus* Smith (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Pimplinae) from South Korea with descriptions of two new species. - Zootaxa. 4132 (2): 235-253.
- Clark M.E. 1956. An annotated list of the Coleoptera taken at or near Terrace, British Columbia. Part III. - Proceedings of the Entomological Society of British Columbia. 52: 39-43.
- Costello S.L., Jacobi W.R. & Negrón J.F. 2013. Emergence of Buprestidae, Cerambycidae, and Scolytinae (Coleoptera) from Mountain Pine Beetle-Killed and Fire-Killed Ponderosa Pines in the Black Hills, South Dakota, USA. - The Coleopterists' Bulletin. 67 (2): 149-154.
- Craighead F.C. 1923. North American Cerambycid Larvae. A classification and the biology of North American Cerambycid Larvae. - Bulletin of the Canada Department of Agriculture (N.S.). 27: 1-239.
- Craighead F.C. 1950. Insects Enemies of Eastern Forests. - USDA Miscellaneous Publications, Washington D.C. 657: 1-679, figs 1-197.
- Curtis J. 1839. British entomology; being illustrations and descriptions of the genera of insects found in Great Britain & Ireland: containing coloured figures from nature of the most rare and beautiful species, & in many instances of the plants upon which they are found. - British entomology. 16: 722-769.
- Danilevsky M.L. 1982. Little known species of timber-beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from Talysh. - Revue d'Entomologie. 61 (4): 809-816. [in Russian]
- Danilevsky M.L. 2009. Species Group Taxa of Longhorned Beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) Described by N. N. Plavilstshikov and Their Types Preserved in the Zoological Museum of the Moscow State University and in the Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences, St. Petersburg. - Entomological Review. 89 (6): 689-720.

M.A. Lazarev

- Danilevsky M.L. 2014. Longicorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycoidea) of Russia and adjacent countries. Part 1. Moscow: Higher School Consulting 1: 522 pp.
- Danilevsky M.L. & Miroshnikov A.I. 1985. Timber-Beetles of Caucasus (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). Key. Krasnodar: 419 pp. [in Russian]
- Danilevsky M.L. & Smetana A. 2010. [Cerambycidae taxa from Russia and countries of former Soviet Union, and Mongolia] A. Drumont & Z. Komiya. Subfamily Prioninae, pp. 86-95; G. Sama, I. Löbl, K. Adlbauer, L. Hubweber, J. Morati, P. Rapuzzi, A. Weigel. Subfamily Philinae to subfamily Parandrinae: pp. 84-86; subfamilies Lepturinae to Lamiinae [without Apatophyseinae and Dorcadionini]: pp. 95-241, 264-334. - In: I. Löbl & A. Smetana (ed.): Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera, Vol. 6. Stenstrup: Apollo Books. 924 pp.
- DeLeon D. 1934. An annotated list of the parasites, predators, and other associated fauna of the mountain pine beetle in western white pine and lodgepole pine. - The Canadian Entomologist. 66 (3): 51-61.
- Denux O. 2005. Contribution à l'inventaire des Cerambycidae (Insecta, Coleoptera) du Parc naturel régional du Perche. - L'Entomologiste. 61 (5): 227-237.
- Dillon L.S. & Dillon E.S. 1961. A manual of common beetles of eastern North America. Evanston, Illinois. Row, Peterson & Co. 2: 435-894, figs 345-544, 81 pls.
- Dimmock G. 1871. Miscellaneous notes. Coleoptera. - The Canadian Entomologist. 3 (1): 15-16.
- Doane R.W., Dyke E.C. Van, Chamberlin W.J. & Burke H.E. 1936. Forest Insects. A Textbook for the Use of Students in Forest School, Colleges and Universities, and for Forest Workers. New York & London, McGraw-Hill Book Co., 463 pp, 234 figs + frontispice.
- Dobrosavljević J. & Mihajlović L. 2014. Contribution to the knowledge on Longhorn Beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of Serbia, with reference to protected species. - Sumarstvo. (1-2): 21-31.
- Dodelin C. & Sauvagère M. 2009. Cerambycidae de Haute-Normandie. Premier bilan sur les données anciennes et récentes, perspectives de recherche dans un but d'actualisation du catalogue régional. - Bulletin de l'Association Entomologique d'Evreux. 56-57: 1-35.
- Dovhaniuk I.Y. & Zamoroka A.M. 2020. The longhorn beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of National Park «Kremenetski Hory». - Proceedings of the State Natural History Museum. 36: 129-140.
- Drouin G. 1991. Chasses printanières au Québec, Canada. - Lambillionea. 91 (3): 170-177.
- Duffy E.A.J. 1953. A monograph of the immature stages of British and imported timber beetles (Cerambycidae). - British Museum (Natural History), London: viii + 350 pp, 8 pls, 292 figs.
- Duffy E.A.J. 1960. A monograph of the immature stages of Neotropical timber beetles (Cerambycidae). - British Museum (Natural History), London: vii + 327, 176 figs & 13 pls, frontispice.
- Easterling G.R. 1934. A study of the insect fauna of a coniferous reforestation area in Southeastern Ohio. - The Ohio Journal of Science. 34 (3): 129-146.

M.A. Lazarev

- Ehnström B & Holmer M. 2007. Nationalnyckeln till Sveriges flora och fauna. Skalbaggar: Långhorningar Coleoptera: Cerambycidae. ArtDatabank, SLU, Uppsala. 302 pp.
- Emmons E. 1854. Agriculture of New York; comprising an account of the classification, composition and distribution of the soils...; together with descriptions of the more common and injurious species of insects. - The Natural History of New York. Agricultural Report. 5: 1-276, 47 pls.
- Engelhardt G.P. 1912. In Proceedings of the New York Entomological Society. Meeting of May 7, 1912. - Journal of the New York Entomological Society. 20 (3): 221-223.
- Ericson I.B. 1916. Rhagium Iberonis I. B. Erics, n. sp. - Entomologisk Tidskrift. 37: 240.
- Essig E.O. 1926. Insects of Western North America. New York, MacMillan Co.: viii-ix + 1-1035, 766 figs.
- Evans J.D. 1895. The insect fauna of the Sudbury District, Ontario. - The Canadian Entomologist. 27 (7): 173-175.
- Fabricius J.C. 1781. Species insectorum exhibentes eorum differentias specificas, synonyma auctorum, loca natalia, metamorphosin adiectis observationibus, descriptionibus. Hamburgi et Kilonii: Carol Ernest Bohnii 1: iii-viii + 1-552.
- Fabricius J.C. 1775. Systema Entomologiae, sistens insectorum classes, ordines, genera, species, adiectis synonymis, locis, descriptionibus, observationibus. Officina Libraria Kortii; Flensburgi & Lipsiae 30 + 832 pp.
- Fabricius J.C. 1776. Genera insectorum eorumque characteres naturales secundum numerum, figuram, situm et proportionem omnium partium oris adiecta mantissa specierum nuper detectarum. Chilonii, Michae Friedrich Bartsch: i-xv + 1-310.
- Fabricius J.C. 1787. Mantissa insectorum, sistens eorum species nuper detectas adiectis characteribus genericis, differentiis specificis, emendationibus, observationibus. Tomus I. Hafniae: C. G. Proft, xx + 348 pp.
- Fabricius J.C. 1793. Entomologia systematica emendata et aucta, secundum classes, ordines, genera, species, adiectis, synonymis, locis, observationibus, descriptionibus. Tomus I. Pars II. Hafniae: C. G. Proft, xx + 538 pp.
- Fabricius J.C. 1802. Systema eleutheratorum secundum ordines, genera, species, adiectis synonymis, locis, observationibus, descriptionibus. Tomus II. Kiliae: Bibliopoli Academici Novi, 687 pp.
- Facon D. 2016. Les Longicornes (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) du Montreuillois: données nouvelles pour la période 2007-2016. - Bulletin de la Société Entomologique du Nord de la France. 361: 2-14.
- Fall H.C. 1901. List of the Coleoptera of southern California with notes on habits and descriptions of new species. - Occasional Papers of the California Academy of Sciences. 8: 1-282.
- Fall H.C. & Cockerell T.D.A. 1907. The Coleoptera of New Mexico. - Transactions of the American Entomological Society. 33: 145-272.
- Fauvel C.A.A. 1889. Liste des Coléoptères communs à l'Europe et à l'Amérique du Nord. - Revue d'Entomologie, Caen. 8: 92-174.
- Fattig P.W. 1947. The Cerambycidae or long-horned beetles of Georgia. - Emory University Museum Bulletin. 5: 1-48.

M.A. Lazarev

- Felt E.P. 1903. Insects Affecting Forest Trees. - New York Forest Fish & Game Comm., Seventh Report: 479-534.
- Felt E.P. 1906. Insects affecting park and woodland trees. - Memoirs of the New York State Museum. 8 (142): 333-877, figs 64-223 + pls 49-70.
- Fisher W.S. & Kirk H.B. 1912. Cerambycidae from Harrisburg, Pennsylvania, and vicinity, with notes (Coleop.). - Entomological News, Philadelphia. 23 (7): 308-316.
- Fletcher F.C. 1926. A preliminary biological survey of the Lloyd-Cornell Reservation. - Bulletin of the Lloyd Library. 5 (27): 1-221.
- Fuller A.S. 1875. Correspondence. Rhagium lineatum. - The Canadian Entomologist. 7 (5): 96-100.
- Ganglbauer L. 1882a. Bestimmungs-Tabellen der europäischen Coleopteren. VII. Cerambycidae. Verhandlungen der Kaiserlich-Königlichen Zoologisch-Botanischen Gesellschaft in Wien. 31 (1881): 681-758, pl. 22.
- Ganglbauer L. 1882b. Bestimmungs-Tabellen der europäischen Coleopteren. Cerambycidae. 7. 79 pp.
- Gardiner L.M. 1957. Deterioration of fire-killed pine in Ontario and the causal wood-boring beetles. - The Canadian Entomologist. 89 (6): 241-263.
- Gardiner L.M. 1966. Egg bursters and hatching in the Cerambycidae (Coleoptera). - Canadian Journal of Zoology. 44: 199-212, 57 figs.
- Gardiner L.M. 1970. Biological Notes on some Nearctic Lepturinae (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). - The Pan-Pacific Entomologist. 46 (4): 284-288.
- Garnett R.T. 1918. An annotated list of the Cerambycidae of California. (Continued from page 177.). - The Canadian Entomologist. 50 (6): 205-213.
- Gebler F.A. von, 1830. Bemerkungen über die Insekten Sibiriens, vorzüglich des Altai. (Part III). S. 1-228. - In: C.F. Ledebour (ed.): Reise durch das Altai-Gebirge und die soongorische Kirgisen-Steppe. Auf Kosten der Kaiserlichen Universität Dorpat unternommen im Jahre 1826 in Begleitung der Herren D. Carl Anton Meyer und D. Alexander von Bunge R.K. Collegien-Assessors. Zweiter Theil. Berlin: G. Reimer, iv + 522 + 228S.
- Gebler F.A.von, 1848. Verzeichniss der im Kolywano-Woskresenskischen Hüttenbezirke süd-west Sibiriens beobachteten Käfer mit Bemerkungen und Beschreibungen.- Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou. 21 (2): 317-423.
- Gemminger M. 1872. Cerambycidae. Pp. 2751-2988. In: Gemminger M. & Harold E. von: Catalogus Coleopterorum hucusque descriptorum synonymicus et systematicus. Tom IX. Scolytidae, Brenthidae, Anthotribidae, Cerambycidae. Monachii: E. H. Gummi, [1] + 2669- 2988 + [12] pp.
- Geoffroy É.L. 1762. Histoire abrégée des insectes qui se trouvent aux environs de Paris; Dans laquelle ces Animaux sont rangés suivant un ordre méthodique. Durand, Paris 1: 1-523, pls I-X. (nomenclature non binomiale)
- Glover T. 1869. The food and habits of beetles. - USDA Report of the Commission of Agriculture, Washington: 78-117.
- Gmelin J.F. 1790. Caroli a Linné Systema Naturæ per Regna tria Naturæ, secundum Classes, Ordines, Genera, Species, cum characteribus, differentiis, synonymis, locis. Classis V. Insecta. Editio 13. Lipsiæ, Georg Emanuel

M.A. Lazarev

- Beer. 1 (4): 1517-2224.
- Gressitt J.L. 1951. Longicorn beetles of China. In: Lepesme P.: Longicornia, études et notes sur les longicornes, Volume 2. Paris: Paul Lechevalier. 667 pp., 22 pls
- Gressitt J.L. 1953. Notes on Nomenclature and Relationships of some Palearctic and Nearctic Lepturinae (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). - The Pan-Pacific Entomologist. 29 (4): 207.
- Grosso-Silva J.M. 2000. Registos interessantes de Cerambycídeos (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) para Portugal. - Boletín de la Sociedad Entomológica Aragonesa. 27: 39-41.
- Gosling D.C.L. & Gosling N.M. 1976. An annotated list of the Cerambycidae of Michigan (Coleoptera) Part II, the subfamilies Lepturinae and Lamiinae. - The Great Lakes Entomologist, Detroit. 10 (1): 1-37.
- Gosling D.C.L. 1986. Ecology of the Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) of the Huron Mountains in Northern Michigan. - The Great Lakes Entomologist. 19 (3): 153-162.
- Haack R.A., Keena M.A. & Eyre D. 2017. Life History and Population Dynamics of Cerambycids. Pp. 71-103.- In: Qiao Wang (ed.) Cerambycidae of the World: Biology and Pest Management. CRC Press. 628 pp.
- Haack R.A. 2020. Buprestidae, Cerambycidae, and Siricidae Collected in Baited Funnel Traps on Drummond Island, Chippewa County, Michigan, - The Great Lakes Entomologist. 53 (1-2): 73-82.
- Haldeman S.S. 1847. Material towards a history of the Coleoptera Longicornia of the United States. - Transactions of the American Philosophical Society. (2) 10: 27-66.
- Hanham A.W. 1894. Notes on Quebec Coleoptera. - The Canadian Entomologist. 26 (12): 350-352.
- Hansen V. 1966. Biller XXII. TRÆBUKKE. Danmarks Fauna, Dansk Naturhistorisk Forening, København, Band 73: 1-228.
- Hamilton J. 1894a. Catalogue of the Coleoptera of Alaska, with the synonymy and distribution. - Transactions of the American Entomological Society. 21: 1-38.
- Hamilton J. 1894b. Catalogue of the Coleoptera common to North America, northern Asia and Europe, with the distribution and bibliography (2nd edition). - Transactions of the American Entomological Society. 21: 345-416.
- Harde V. 1966. 87. Familie: Cerambycidae, Bockkäfer. In: Freude H., Harde K.W. & Lohse G.A. Die Käfer Mitteleuropas. Bd. 9: 7-94.
- Hardy G.A. 1926. Cerambycidae of Vancouver Island. (Preliminary annotated list). - Report of the Province of British Columbia Museum of Natural History. (1925): 1-10.
- Hardy G.A. & Preece W.H.A. 1926. Notes on some species of Cerambycidae (Col.) from the southern portion of Vancouver Island, B.C. - The Pan-Pacific Entomologist. 3 (1): 33-40.
- Hardy G.A. 1927. Report on a collecting trip to Garibaldi Park, B.C. - Report of the Province of British Columbia Museum of Natural History. (1926): C15-C26.
- Hardy G.A. 1948. Some beetles of the families Cerambycidae and Buprestidae from

M.A. Lazarev

- Manning Park, British Columbia. - Proceedings of the Entomological Society of British Columbia. 44: 31-34.
- Hardy G.A. 1955. The natural history of the Forbidden Plateau area Vancouver Island, British Columbia. - Report of the British Columbia Province Museum of Natural History and Anthropology. (1954): B24-B63, 1 map.
- Harrington W.H. 1881. On some Coleoptera injurious to our pines. - Transactions of the Ottawa Field Naturalists' Club. 2: 28-33.
- Harris T.W. 1838. Habits of some of the insects injurious to vegetation in Massachusetts. - Reports of the Commissioners on the Zoological Survey of the State: 57-104.
- Harris T.W. 1841. A report on the insects of Massachusetts injurious to vegetation. Cambridge, Massachusetts. 459 pp.
- Hatch M.H. 1971. The beetles of the Pacific Northwest. Part V: Rhipicerioidea, Sternoxi, Phytophaga, Rhynchophora, and Lamellicornia. University of Washington Publications in Biology, Seattle. 16: 1-662, 55 pls.
- Hayashi M. 1960. Study of the Lepturinae (Col.: Cerambycidae). - Niponius. 1 (6): 1-26.
- Hayashi M. 1963. Revision of some Cerambycidae on the basis of the types of the late Drs. Kano and Matsushita, with descriptions of three new species. - Insecta Matsumurana. 25: 129-136.
- Heffern D.J. 1998. Insects of Western North America. 1. A Survey of the Cerambycidae (Coleoptera), or Longhorned Beetles, of Colorado. Contributions of the C.P. Gillette Museum of Arthropod Diversity Department of Bioagricultural Sciences and Pest Management Colorado State University: 1-32.
- Herrick G.W. 1935. Insect enemies of shade trees. Comstock Publisher Company. Ithaca, New York. 417 pp, 321 figs.
- Hess W.N. 1917. The chordotonal organs and pleural discs of cerambycidae larvae. - Annals of the Entomological Society of America, Columbus. 10 (1): 63-74.
- Hess W.N. 1920. The ribbed pine borer. - Memoir of the Cornell University Agricultural Experiment Station. 33: 367-381.
- Heyrovský L. 1955. Fauna ČSR. Svazek 5. Tesarikoviti (Cerambycidae). Praha, Československa Akademie Ved. Sekce biol. 346 pp, 70 figs.
- Holland W.J. 1888. Captures made while travelling from Winnipeg to Victoria, B.C. -The Canadian Entomologist. 20 (5): 89-92.
- Holt B.D. 2013. A Preliminary Checklist of the Cerambycidae and Disteniidae (Coleoptera) of Alabama. - The Coleopterists' Bulletin. 67 (3): 241-256.
- Hopkins A.D. 1893. Catalogue of West Virginia forest and shade tree insects collected in 1890-1893, including injurious, beneficial and other insects taken on or in some part of the tree examined. - Bulletin of the West Virginia University Agricultural Experiment Station. 32 (8): 171-251.
- Hopkins A.D. 1899. Report on investigations to determine the cause of unhealthy conditions of the spruce and pine from 1880-1893. - Bulletin of the West Virginia University Agricultural Experiment Station. 56: 197-461.
- Hopkins A.D. 1904. Catalogue of exhibits of insect enemies of forest and forest products at the Louisiana Purchase Exposition St. Louis, Mo. 1904. -

M.A. Lazarev

- USDA Division of Entomology Bulletin (N. S.). 48: 1-56, 22 pls.
- Hopping R. 1937. The Lepturini of America North of Mexico - Part II. Canadian Department of Mines Resources. - Canadian National Museum Bulletin 85, Biology Series. 22: 1-42.
- Horn G.H. 1876. Synonymy of the Coleoptera of the Fauna Boreali-Americana, Kirby. - The Canadian Entomologist. 8 (9): 166-170.
- Horn G.H. 1886. A review of the species described by Olivier in the «Entomologie». - Transactions of the American Entomological Society. 13: 135-144.
- Howden H.F. & Vogt G.B. 1951. Insect communities of standing dead pine (*Pinus virginiana* Mill.). - Annals of the Entomological Society of America, Columbus. 44 (4): 581-595, 4 figs.
- Iiinsky A.I. 1962. Identifier of forest pests. Moscow, Selkhozizdat. 392 pp. [in Russian]
- Ingles L.G. 1933. The succession of insects in tree trunks shown by collections from various stages of decay. - Journal of Entomology and Zoology, Claremont. 25: 57-59.
- Jaques H.E. 1951. How To Know the Beetles. Dubuque, Iowa; William C. Brown Co.: i-vi + 1-372, 865 figs.
- Kadyrbekov R.Kh. & Tleppeeva A.M. 1997. Ecological and faunistic review of longhorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of the Almaty Reserve. - News of the Ministry of Science - Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Kazakhstan, Biological and Medical Series. 1: 40-44. [in Russian]
- Kadyrbekov R.Kh., Childebaev M.K. & Yashchenko R.V. 1996. On the distribution and ecology of six species of longhorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of the fauna of Kazakhstan. - Bulletin of the National Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Kazakhstan, Biological Series. 5, 191, 1995 (1996): 86-49. [in Russian]
- Kaszab Z. 1971. Cincérek - Cerambycidae. Fauna Hungariae. 106. Kötet 9. Coleoptera 4. Füzet 5. Budapest: Akadémia Kiadó: 283 + 17 p.
- Keen F.P. 1929. Insect enemies of California pines and their control. - California Department of Natural Resources Division of Forestry Bulletin. 7: 1-113.
- Keen J.H. 1895. List of Coleoptera collected at Massett, Queen Charlotte Islands, B.C. - The Canadian Entomologist. 27 (8): 217-220.
- Kimmy J.W. & Furniss R.L. 1943. Deterioration of fire killed Douglas fir. - USDA Technical Bulletin. 851: 1-61.
- Kirby W. 1837. Part the fourth and last. The insects. - In: Richardson J.: Fauna Boreali-Americana; or the zoology of the northern parts of British America: containing descriptions of the objects of natural history collected on the late Northern Land Expedition, under command of captain Sir John Franklin, R. N. Norwich: J. Fletcher, xxxix + 325 + [1] pp., 8 pl.
- Kirk H.B. & Knull J.N. 1926. Annotated list of the Cerambycidae of Pennsylvania. - The Canadian Entomologist. 58 (1): 21-26.
- Kirk V.M. & Balsbaugh E.U. 1975. A list of the beetles of South Dakota. - South Dakota State University Agricultural Experiment Station Technical Bulletin, Bookings. 42: 1-139.
- Klausnitzer B., Klausnitzer U., Wachmann E. & Hromádko Z., 2016. Die Bockkäfer

M.A. Lazarev

- Mitteleuropas. Cerambycidae. Band 2: Die mitteleuropäischen Arten. - Die Neue Brehm-Bücherei. 499 (2): 3-303.
- Klingeman W.E., Youssef N.N., Oliver J.B. & Basham J.P., 2017. The Longhorned Beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of Tennessee: Distribution of Species, Seasonal Adult Activity, and New State Records. - Florida Entomologist. 100 (2): 292-302.
- Knowlton G.F. & Thatcher T.O. 1936. Notes on wood-boring beetles. - The Utah Academy of Sciences, Arts and Letters. 13: 277-281.
- Knowlton G.F. & Wood S.L. 1950. An annotated list of Utah Cerambycidae. - Bulletin of the Brooklyn Entomological Society. 45 (1): 10-13.
- Knoll J.N. 1946. The long-horned beetles of Ohio (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). - Bulletin of the Ohio Biological Survey. 7 (4) 39: 133-354.
- König E. 1899. Coleoptera Caucasica. S. 339-403. [Cerambycidae: S. 393-397] - In: Radde G. Die Summlungen des Kauasischen Museums. 1. Tiflis. 521 s.
- Kolbe H.J. 1884. Die Entwicklungsstadien der Rhagium-Arten und des Rhamnusium salicis, nebst einer vergleichend-systematischen Untersuchung der Larven und Imagines dieser Gattungen und ihrer Species. - Entomologische Nachrichten. 10 (16): 237-250.
- Krivolutskaya G.O. 1965. Hidden-stemmed pests in dark coniferous forests of Western Siberia damaged by the Siberian silkworm. Moscow-Leningrad, "Nauka". 129 pp.
- Krivoshaina N.P. & Kompantsev A.V. 1984. The main groups of wood destroyers and their entomophages in the forests of the Kostroma region. - In: Animal world of the southern taiga. Problems and methods of research. Moscow: "Nauka": 165-190.
- Küster H.C. 1848. Die Käfer Europa's. Nach der Natur beschrieben. Mit Beiträgen mehrerer Entomologen. 15. Heft. Nürnberg: Bauer & Raspe, [4] + 100 sheets, 3 pls
- Lacordaire J.T. 1868. Histoire Naturelle des Insectes. Genera des Coléoptères ou exposé méthodique et critique de tous les genres proposés jusqu'ici dans cet ordre d'insectes. Paris. Librairie Encyclopédique de Roret. 8: 1-552.
- Lagos Ordoñez M.E. & Nápoles J.R. 2024. Los Cerambycidos (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) de la colección de insectos de Colpos-Montecillo, México [Cerambycids (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of te insect collection of Colpos-Montecillo, Mexico]. - Folia Entomológica Mexicana (nueva serie). 10 (e20241003): 1-52.
- Laliberté J.L., Chantal C. & Larochelle A. 1977. Ecologie des longicornes du Québec. - Fabriques. 3: 88-102.
- Lamarck J.-B.A.P. 1801. Système des animaux sans vertèbres ou tableau général des classes, des ordres et des genres de ces animaux. Deterville, Paris. 432 pp.
- Lamarck J.-B.A.P. 1817. Histoire naturelle des animaux sans vertèbres. Paris. 4. 603 pp.
- Lange W.H. 1937. An annotated list of the insects, mostly Coleoptera, associated with Jeffrey pine in Lassen National Forest, California. - The Pan-Pacific Entomologist. 13 (4): 172-175.
- Laporte [= de Castelnau] F.L.N. de Caumont. 1840. Histoire naturelle des insectes coléoptères. Tome deuxième. Histoire naturelle des animaux articulés,

M.A. Lazarev

- annelides, crustacés, arachnides, myriapodes et insectes. Tome troisième. Paris: P. Duméril. 564 pp., 38 pls.
- Latreille P.-A. 1804. Histoire Naturelle, Générale et particulière des Crustacés et des Insectes. Imprimerie F. Dufart, Paris 11: iv + 1-424, pls 91-93.
- Laurent P. 1895. Notes on the insect fauna of Somerset Co., Maine. - *The Canadian Entomologist*. 27 (11): 322-324.
- Lazarev M.A. 2024. Taxonomic notes on longhorned beetles with the descriptions of several new taxa (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). - *Humanity space. International almanac*. 13 (1): 21-38.
- Leech H.B. 1947. Collecting in southern British Columbia: Hilltop to lake-shore for beetles. - *The Canadian Entomologist*. 79 (6): 105-108.
- Leach W.E. 1819. [new taxa]. - In: G. Samuelle: *The Entomologist's useful compendium; Or an introduction to the knowledge of British Insects, comprising the best means of obtaining and preserving them, and a description of the apparatus generally used; together with the genera of Linné, and the modern method of arranging the classes Crustacea, Myriapoda, spiders, mites, and insects from their affinities and structure, according to the views of Dr. Leach. Also an explanation of the terms used in entomology; A calendar of the times of appearance, and usual situations of near 3000 species of British insects; With instructions for collecting and fitting up objects for the microscope*. London: Thomas Boys, 496 pp., xii pls.
- Leconte J.L. 1850a. General remarks upon the Coleoptera of Lake Superior. - In: Agassiz. *Lake Superior, its physical character, vegetation, and animals*. Boston: 461 pp.
- Leconte J.L. 1850b. An attempt to classify the Longicorn Coleoptera of the part of America North of Mexico. - *Journal of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia* (ser. 2). 1: 311-340.
- Leconte J.L. 1854. Some corrections in the Nomenclature of Coleoptera found in the United States. - *Proceedings of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia*. 7: 216-220.
- Leconte J.L. 1873. Classification of the Coleoptera of North America. Prepared for the Smithsonian Institution. Part II. - *Smithsonian Miscellaneous Collections*. Washington, D.C. 11 (265): 279-348.
- Leconte J.L. 1874. On some changes in the nomenclature of North American Coleoptera, which have been recently proposed. - *The Canadian Entomologist*. 6 (10): 186-196.
- Leconte J.L. 1879. The Coleoptera of the Alpine Rocky Mountain Regions. - Part II. - *Bulletin of the United States Geological and Geographical Survey of the Territory*. 5 (3): 499-520.
- Leconte J.L. & Horn G.H. 1883. Classification of the Coleoptera of North America. Prepared for the Smithsonian Institution. *Smithsonian Miscellaneous Collections*. Washington, D.C. 26 (507): i-xxvii + 1-567.
- Leng C.W. 1890. Synopses of Cerambycidae. - *Entomologica Americana*. Brooklyn. 6 (4): 65-69.
- Leonard M.D. 1928. A list of the insects of New York with a list of the spiders and certain other allied groups. - *Memoir of the Cornell University Agricultural*

M.A. Lazarev

- Experiment Station, Ithaca. 101: 1-1121, 1 map.
- Lindemann K. 1871. Review of geographical distribution of Coleoptera of Russian Empire. Part I. Introduction, preface, Northern, Moscow and Turan provinces. - *Horae Societatis Entomologicae Rossicae*. 6 (1-4): 41-366. [in Russian]
- Lindhe A., Jeppsson T. & Ehnström B. 2011. Longhorn beetles in Sweden - changes in distribution and abundance over the last two hundred years. - *Entomologisk Tidskrift*. 131 (4) (2010): 241-512.
- Lingafelter S.W., Nearn E.H., Tavakilian G.L., Monné M.A. & Biondi M. 2014. Longhorned Woodboring Beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae and Disteniidae) Primary Types of the Smithsonian Institution. Smithsonian Institution Scholarly Press, Washington D.C.: v-xviii + 1-390, 187 figs.
- Linnaeus [= Linné] C. 1758. *Systema naturæ per regna tria naturæ secundum classes, ordines, genera, species, cum characteribus, differentiis, synonymis, locis. Systema naturae (Editio 10) Laur. Salvius. Holmiae*. 1: iii + 824 pp.
- Linnaeus [= Linné] C. 1761. *Fauna Svecica sistens Animalia Sueciæ Regni: Mammalia, Aves, Amphibia, Pisces, Insecta, Vermes. Distributa per Classes & Ordines, Genera & Species, cum Differentiis Specierum, Synonymis Auctorum, Nominibus Incolarum, Locis Natalium Descriptionibus Insectorum. Sumtu & Literis Direct. Laurentii Salvii, Stockholmiae (1760): i-xlvi + 1-578, 2 pls.*
- Linnaeus [= Linné] C. 1767. *Systema Naturae. Editio Duodecima Reformata. Laurent Salvius, Holmiae*. 1 (2): 533-1327.
- Linsley E.G. & Chemsak J.A. 1972. *Cerambycidae of North America, Part VI, No. 1. Taxonomy and classification of the subfamily Lepturinae. University of California Publications in Entomology, Berkeley* 69: viii + 1-138, 41 figs & 2 pls.
- Linsley E.G. & Chemsak J.A. 1997. *The Cerambycidae of North America, Part VIII: Bibliography, Index, and Host Plant Index. University of California Press, Berkeley* 117: i-ix + 1-534.
- Lim J., Jung S.-Y., Lim J.-S., Jang J., Kim K.-M., Lee Y.-M. & Lee B.-W. 2014. A Review of Host Plants of Cerambycidae (Coleoptera: Chrysomeloidea) with new Host Records for Fourteen Cerambycids, Including the Asian Longhorn Beetle (*Anoplophora glabripennis* Motschulsky), in Korea. - *Korean Journal of Applied Entomology*. 53 (2): 111-133.
- Lobanov A.L., Danilevsky M.L. & Murzin S.V. 1981. Systematic list of longicorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of the USSR. 1.- *Revue d'Entomologie*. 60 (4): 784-803. [in Russian]
- Löding H.P. 1945. *Catalogue of the beetles of Alabama. Geological Survey of Alabama Monograph*. 11: 1-172.
- MacRae T.C. 1993. Annotated checklist of the longhorned beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae and Disteniidae) occurring in Missouri. - *Insecta Mundi*. 7 (4): 223-252.
- Maeklin F.W. 1857. Beitrag zur Kenntniss der geographischen Verbreitung der Insecten im Norden mit besonderer Berücksichtigung der Fauna Scandinaviens und Finlands. - *Stettiner Entomologische Zeitung*. 18: 171-192.
- Mamaev B.M. & Danilevsky M.L. 1975 *Larvae of Timber Beetles. Moscow: Nauka*. 282 pp. [in Russian]

M.A. Lazarev

- Mank E.W. 1934. The Coleoptera of Glacier Park, Montana. - The Canadian Entomologist. 66 (4): 73-81.
- Mann B.P. 1886. [Communications]. - Proceedings of the Entomological Society of Washington. 1 (1): 27.
- Mannerheim C.G. 1852. Zweiter Nachtrag zur Kaefer-Fauna der Nord-Amerikanischen Laender des Russischen Reiches. - Bulletin de la Société Impériale des Naturalistes de Moscou. 25 (1) 2: 283-387.
- Martínez Hernández J.G., Rös M., Pérez-Flores Ó. & Toledo-Hernández V.H. 2024. Checklist of the Cerambycidae (Coleoptera: Chrysomeloidea) of Oaxaca, Mexico. - Zootaxa. 5405 (2): 185-208.
- Matsumura S. 1911. Erster Beitrag zur Insekten-Fauna von Sachalin. - The Journal of the College of Agriculture, Tohoku Imperial University. 4 (1): 1-145.
- Martynov V.V. & Pisarenko T.A., 2004. A review of the fauna and ecology of the long-horned beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of southeast Ukraine. - The Kharkov Entomological Society Gazette. 11 (2003) (1-2): 44-69. [in Russian]
- Melsheimer F.E. 1853. Catalogue of the described Coleoptera of the United States. Washington, D.C., Smithsonian Institution xvi + 174 pp.
- Micas L. 2005. Le vallon de la Moulinière (Alpes-de-Haute-Provence): biodiversité coléoptérologique. I. Cerambycidae. - L'Entomologiste. 61 (4): 145-148.
- Migliaccio E., Georgiev G. & Mirchev P. 2004. Studies on Cerambycid Fauna (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of the Vitosha Mountain, Bulgaria. - Acta Zoologica Bulgarica. 56 (2): 137-144.
- Monné M.Á. 1995. Catalogue of the Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) of the western hemisphere. Part XXI. Subfamily Lepturinae. Sociedade Brasileira de Entomologia, São Paulo. 21: 1-159.
- Monné M.Á. & Giesbert E.F. 1994. Checklist of the Cerambycidae and Disteniidae (Coleoptera) of the Western Hemisphere. Wolfsgarden Books. Burbank, California: i-xiv + 1-410.
- Moody H.L. 1875. Correspondence. Rhagium lineatum. - The Canadian Entomologist. 7 (5): 96.
- Morris F.J.A. 1908. «Some beetle-haunts» by an amateur botanist. - The Canadian Entomologist. 40 (12): 441-449.
- Morris F.J.A. 1916. Reports on insects of the year. Division No. 5, Port Hope District. - In: 46th Annual Report of the Entomological Society of the Province of Ontario. (1915): 17-21.
- Motschulsky V. 1859. Catalogue des insectes rapportés des environs du fl. Amour, depuis la Schilka jusqu'à Nikolaëvsk. - Bulletin de la Société Impériales des Naturalistes de Moscou, 32 (4): 487-507. [note: reprinted separately in 1860, Moscou, Imprimerie de l'Université Impériale, 21 pp.]
- Motschulsky [Motchoulski] V. 1860a. Coléoptères rapportés de la Songarie par M. Semenof et décrits par V. de Motshoulski. - Bulletin de l'Académie Impériale des Sciences de St. Pétersbourg. 1: 301-314.
- Motschulsky V. 1860c. Coléoptères rapportés de la Sibérie orientale et notamment des pays situées sur les bords du fleuve Amour par MM. Schrenck, Maak, Ditmar, Voznessenski etc. détermines et décrits par V. de Motschulsky. [Coléoptères de la Sibérie orientale et en particulier des rives de l'Amour]. -

M.A. Lazarev

- In: Dr. L. v. Schrenck's Reisen und Forschungen im Amur-Lande. Band 2. Coleopteren: 79-257, Tab. VI-XI + Carte.
- Müller G. 1949-50. 1. Fam. Cerambycidae. Pp. 15-224. - In: I coleotteri della Venezia Giulia. Catalogo regionato con tabelle dichotomiche per la classificazione delle specie della regione adriatica orientale, del Veneto e della pianura padana. Volume II: Coleoptera Phytophaga (Cerambycidae, Chrysomelidae, Bruchidae). Trieste: Centro sperimentale agrario e forestale (Pubblicazione N. 4) [1949-1953], 685 + [1] pp. [note: issued in parts: pp. 1-80 in 1949, 81-224 in 1950, 225-368 in 1951, 369-480 in 1952, 481-685 in 1953].
- Mulsant É. 1839. Histoire Naturelle des Coléoptères de France. Longicornes. Maison Libraire, Paris. Imprimerie de Dumoulin, Ronet et Sibuet, Lyon: vii-xii + 1-304 pp., 3 pls.
- Mulsant E. 1863. Histoire naturelle des coléoptères de France. Longicornes. [Pp. 1-480]. Ed. 2. Paris: Magnin, Blanchard et Cie, successeurs de Louis Janet, 590 pp.
- Mundinger F.G. 1924. A preliminary list of Buprestidae and Cerambycidae of the Cranberry Lake region, New York. - Technical Publications of the New York State College of Forestry. 17: 313-320.
- Nicolay A.S. 1917. Buprestidae and Cerambycidae from Maine. - Bulletin of the Brooklyn Entomological Society. 12 (4): 92-95.
- Nicolay A.S. 1919. A list of the Buprestidae and Cerambycidae taken on Long Island. - Bulletin of the Brooklyn Entomological Society. 14 (2): 63-72.
- Noguera F.A. & Chemsak J.A. 1996. Cerambycidae (Coleoptera). Pp. 381-409. - In: Biodiversidad, Taxonomía y Biogeografía de Artrópodos de México: Hacia una Síntesis de su conocimiento. Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México: 660 pp.
- Ohbayashi N. & Niisato T. 2007. Longicorn Beetles of Japan. Tokai University Press, Kanagawa: v-xii + 1-818, 22 figs, 130 pls couleur.
- Olivier G.A. 1791. Encyclopédie Méthodique. Histoire Naturelle, Insectes. Paris, Plomteux, Liège, Panckoucke Imprimeur-Libraire 6 (1): 1-368.
- Olivier A.G. 1795. Entomologie, ou histoire naturelle des insectes. Avec leur caractères génériques et spécifiques, leur description, leur synonymie, et leur figure enluminée. Coléoptères. Tome quatrième. Paris: de Lanneau, 519 pp. +72 pls. [note: each genus is separately paginated].
- Özdikmen H. 2021a. A naked list of longhorned beetles preferring *Quercus* species as host plant in Turkey (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). - Munis Entomology & Zoology. 16 (1): 439-456.
- Özdikmen H. 2021b. Longhorned beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) preferring *Pinus* species as host plant in Turkey. - Munis Entomology & Zoology. 16 (1): 501-552.
- Özdikmen H. 2024. Turkish members of the genus *Rhagium* Fabricius (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Lepturinae) with new host plants. - Munis Entomology & Zoology. 19 (suppl.): 2704-2712.
- Özdikmen H. & Turgut S. 2010. A synopsis of Turkish *Rhagium* F., 1775 with zoogeographical remarks (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Lepturinae). - Munis Entomology & Zoology. 5 (supplement): 964-976.

M.A. Lazarev

- Pacini A. 2011. Catálogo de escarabajos de cuernos largos (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) de la colección de invertebrados del Museo Provincial de Ciencias Naturales "Florentino Ameghino". - Museo Provincial de Ciencias Naturales "Florentino Ameghino. 26: 1-40.
- Pack H.J. 1930. Notes on Utah Coleoptera. - Entomological News, Philadelphia. 41 (7): 219-222.
- Packard A.S. 1872. Guide to the study of insects, and a treatise on those injurious and beneficial to crops; for the use of colleges, farm-schools and agriculturists. Salem, Naturalists' Agency. Third Edition 702 pp, 651 figs, 15 pls (Appendix pp 703-715).
- Packard A.S. 1881. Insects injurious to forest and shade trees. - Bulletin of the United States Entomological Commission. 7: 1-275.
- Packard A.S. 1890. Insects injurious to forest and shade trees. - In: 5th Report of the United States Entomological Commission, Washington. 7: i-viii + 1-957, 40 pls. (Bull. 7 ed.)
- Palm T. 1959. Die Holz- und Rinden-Käfer der süd- und mittelschwedischen Laubbäume. - Opuscula Entomologica, Supplem. 16: 374.
- Panin S. & Săvulescu N. 1961. Familia Cerambycidae (Croitori). - Fauna Rep. Pop. Romine, Insecta 10 (5), Coleoptera. Bucuresti. 523 pp.
- Parmelee F.T. 1941. Longhorned and flat-headed borers attacking fire-killed coniferous timbers in Michigan. - Journal of Economic Entomology. 34: 377-380.
- Paulus H. 1969. Zur Unterscheidung der Larven der Gattung Rhagium (Col., Cerambycidae, Lamiinae). - Zeitschrift der Arbeitsgemeinschaft Österreichischer Entomologen. 21: 4-11.
- Peck S B. & Thomas M.C. 1998. A distributional checklist of the beetles (Coleoptera) of Florida. - Arthropods of Florida and Neighboring Land Areas. 16: 1-180.
- Perry R.H. 1975. Notes on the long-horned beetles of Virginia, Part III (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). - The Coleopterists' Bulletin. 29 (1): 59.
- Pesarini C. & Sabbadini A. 1995. Insetti della Fauna Europea Coleotteri Cerambycidae. - Natura, Rivista di Scienze Naturali. 85 (1/2): 132 pp.
- Peyerimhoff P.-M. de 1919. Notes sur la biologie de quelques Coléoptères phytophages du Nord-africain (troisième série). - Annales de la Société Entomologique de France. 88: 169-258.
- Picard F. 1929. Coléoptères. Cerambycidae. Faune de France 20. Paris, Paul Lechevalier. 166 pp.
- Planchard F. 1875. Correspondence. Rhagium lineatum. - The Canadian Entomologist. 7: 96-97.
- Planet L. M. 1924: Histoire naturelle des longicornes de France. - Encyclopédie Entomologique. (A) 2. Paris: Lechevalier. 386 pp., 2 pls.
- Plavilstshikov N.N., 1915. Palaearctic species of the genus Rhagium F. (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). - Russian Entomological Review. 15 (1): 32-49.
- Plavilstshikov N.N. 1932. Timber-beetles - Timber Pests. Moscow, Leningrad: 200 pp. [in Russian]
- Plavilstshikov N.N. 1936. Cerambycidae (P.1). In: Faune de l'URSS. Insects

M.A. Lazarev

- Coléptères. V. 21. Moscou, Leningrad. 612 pp. [in Russian]
- Plavilstshikov N.N., 1965. 75-th Fam. Cerambycidae - Timber Beetles, Longicornes.- In: A Key to Insects of the European Part of the USSR, v. 2, Coleoptera and Strepsiptera. Moscow-Leningrad, "Nauka": 389-419. [in Russian]
- Plewa R., Hilszczański J. & Jaworski T. 2014. Kózkowate (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) z kolekcji dr. Bolesława Burakowskiego zebrane podczas wyprawy entomologicznej do Rumunii. [Longhorn beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) collected by Dr. Bolesław Burakowski during entomological expedition to Romania]. - Wiadomości Entomologiczne. 33 (2): 126-138.
- Poda von Neuhaus N. 1761. Insecta Musei Graecensis, quæ in ordines, genera et species Juxta Systema Naturae Caroli Linnæi digessit Nicolaus Poda. Widmanstad iii-viii + 1-127 + index (12 pages), 2 pls.
- Podaný Č. 1964. Monographie des Genus Rhagium Fabricius (Col., Cerambycidae, Stenocorini). - Acta Zoologica Mexicana. 7 (1-3): 1-55.
- Podaný Č. 1978. Nouvelles espèce et sous-espèce de Rhagium F. (Col. Cérambycidae). - Bulletin de la Société Entomologique de Mulhouse: 4.
- Portevin G. 1927. Tableaux dichotomiques pour la détermination des Longicornes de France. - Encyclopédie Entomologique. (A) 2 (supplement): 1-53.
- Procter W. 1927. Biological survey of the Mount Desert Region. Part I. The insect fauna with reference to the flora and other biological features. - Philadelphia Wistar Institute of Anatomy and Biology. 1: 1-247.
- Procter W. 1946. Biological survey of the Mountain Desert Region incorporated. Part VII, being a revision of parts I and IV with the addition of 1100 species. The insect fauna with references to method of capture, food plants, the flora and other biological features. Philadelphia Wistar Institute of Anatomy and Biology. 566 pp, 1 map.
- Provancher L. 1877. Petite faune entomologique du Canada, précédée d'un traité élémentaire d'entomologie. Volume I - Les Coléoptères. Québec, C. Darveau 1: 1-786, 52 figs.
- Rapuzzi P. & Sama G. 2006. Cerambycidae nuovi o interessanti per la fauna di Sicilia (Insecta Coleoptera Cerambycidae). - Quaderni di Studi e Notizie di Storia Naturale della Romagna. 23: 157-172.
- Redtenbacher L. 1874. Fauna Austriaca. Die Käfer nach der analytischen Methode bearbeitet. Wien, Carl Gerold's Sohn 2: 1-571 + i-cliii, 2 pls.
- Reisdorf P., Zagatti P., Doguet S. & Delobel A. 2015. Le Coléoptérisme du Marais de Montabé. Chapitre 5: tableau de bord 2013 et présentation des Chrysomeloidea. - Le Coléoptériste, Bulletin de liaison de l'ACOREP. 18 (3): 152-164.
- Reitter E. 1898. Neue Coleopteren aus Europa und den angrenzenden Ländern. - Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift. 42 (2): 337-360.
- Reitter E. 1913. Fauna Germanica. Die Käfer des Deutschen Reiches. Nach der analytischen Methode bearbeitet. IV. Band. (1912). Stuttgart: K.G. Lutz' Verlag, 236 pp., pl. 129-152.
- Reymond A. 1953. Description de deux formes nouvelles de Cérambycides du

M.A. Lazarev

- Cèdre au Maroc, suivie d'observations sur la biocénose de cet arbre en Afrique du Nord. - Bulletin de la Société des Sciences Naturelles du Maroc. 33: 199-205.
- Rice M.E., MacRae T.C. & Merickel F. 2017. The Longhorned Beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of Idaho. - The Coleopterists' Bulletin. 71 (4): 667-678.
- Riley C.V. 1880. Food habits of the longicorn beetles or wood borers. - The American Entomologist. 3 (10): 237-239.
- Riley C.V. 1883. Descriptions of the larvae of injurious forest insects. - USDA 3rd Report of the United States Entomological Commission: 251-262, pls vi-xv.
- Riley C.V. & Howard L.O. 1889. Damage to dead trunks of pine by *Rhagium lineatum*. - USDA Insect Life, Washington D.C. 2 (6): 190.
- Ross D.A. 1967. Wood and bark-feeding Coleoptera of felled western larch in British Columbia. - Journal of the Entomological Society of British Columbia. 64: 23-24.
- Ross D.A. 1968. Wood and bark-feeding Coleoptera of felled spruce in interior British Columbia. - Journal of the Entomological Society of British Columbia. 65: 10-12.
- Rousset J. 2007. Sur quelques espèces intéressantes capturées près de Saint Amandin (Cantal): *Ceruchus chrysomelinus* Hochenwarth dans le Massif Central. - Le Coléoptériste. Bulletin de liaison de l'ACOREP. 10 (1): 45-47.
- Ruchin A.B., Egorov L.V. & Khapugin A.A. 2022. Vertical Distribution of Beetles (Coleoptera) in Pine Forests in Central European Russia. - Diversity. 14 (622): 1-21.
- Saalas U. 1936. Über das Flügelgeäder und die phylogenetische Entwicklung der Cerambyciden. - Annales Societatis zoologicae-botanicae fennicae Vanamo. 4 (1): 1-198.
- Şabanoglu B. 2020. Faunistic, Ecological, Zoogeographical, and Systematic Evaluation of Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) of the Eastern Black Sea Region of Turkey. - Transactions of the American Entomological Society. 146: 196-219.
- Saikina S.M., Knyazev S.A., Ponomarev K.B., Teploukhov V.Y., Kosheleva T.F. & Dubatolov V.V. 2022. Checklist of longicorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of Omsk Region (Russia). - Acta Biologica Sibirica. 8: 793-819.
- Sama G. 1988. Coleoptera. Cerambycidae. Catalogo topographico e sinonimico. - Fauna d'Italia. 25. 216 pp.
- Sama G. 2003. Atlas of the Cerambycidae of Europe and the Mediterranean Area. Volume 1: Northern, Western, Central and Eastern Europe. British Isles and Continental Europe from France (excl. Corsica) to Scandinavia and Urals. Vít Kabourek, Zlín, (2002): 1-173, 729 figs.
- Sama G. & Rapuzzi P. 2011. Una nuova Checklist dei Cerambycidae d'Italia (Insecta Coleoptera Cerambycidae). - Quaderno di Studi e Notizie di Storia Naturale della Romagna. 32: 121-164
- Savely H.E. 1939. Ecological relations of certain animals in dead pine and oak logs. - Ecological Monographs, Durham. 9: 321-385.
- Schaufuss C.F.C. 1916. Calwer's Käferbuch einföhrung in die Kenntnis der Käfer Europas. Stuttgart, Schweizerbart'sche Verlag (sechste Auflage) 2: 709-1390, figs 251-254, pls 21-48.

M.A. Lazarev

- Schiefer T.L. 1998. A preliminary List of the Cerambycidae and Disteniidae (Coleoptera) of Mississippi. - Transactions of the American Entomological Society. 124 (2): 113-131.
- Schiødte J.M.C. 1865. On the Classification of Cerambyces with particular regard to the Danish Fauna. - The Annals and Magazine of Natural History. 3 (15) 87 (22): 182-209.
- Schneider O. & Leder H. 1879. Beiträge zur Kenntniss der kaukasischen Käferfauna (Sonderabdruck aus dem XVI u. XVII. Bande der Verhandlungen des Naturforschenden Vereins in Brünn). Brünn. 360 s. Taf. I-IV.
- Schoenherr [= Schönherr] C.J. 1808. Synonymia Insectorum, oder: Versuch einer Synonymie aller bisher bekannten Insecten; nach Fabricii Systema Eleutheratorum &c. geordnet. Erster Band. Eleutherata oder Käfer. Zweiter Theil. Spercheus-Cryptocephalus. Stockholm: C.F. Marquard, ix + 424 pp., 1 pl.
- Schoenherr [= Schönherr] C.J. 1817. Synonymia insectorum, oder: Versuch einer Synonymie Aller bisher bekannten Insecten; nach Fabricii Systema Eleutheratorum &c. geordnet. Mit Berichtigungen und Anmerkungen, wie auch Beschreibungen neuer Arten und illuminirten Kupfern. Erster Band. Eleutherata oder Käfer. Skara, Lewerentzischen Buchdrükerey 1 (3): xi + 1-506.
- Schrank F.P. von 1781. Enumeratio Insectorum Austriae indigenorum. August Vindelicor., Klett & Franck: i-xxii + 1-548, 4 pls.
- Schwarz E.A. 1886a. Hibernation of Rhagium lineatum. - Proceedings of the Entomological Society of Washington. 1: 29.
- Schwarz E.A. 1886b. [Habits of Rhagium lineatum]. - Proceedings of the Entomological Society of Washington. 1 (1): 27-28.
- Semenov A.P. 1898. Coleoptera nova Rossiae europaeae Caucasiqae. IV. - Horae Societatis Entomologicae Rossicae. 31 (1897): 595-602.
- Simon H. 2007. Chasses entomologiques particulières en Périgord (Coleoptera). - L'Entomologiste. 63 (3): 155-156.
- Silfverberg H. 2004. Enumeratio nova Coleopterorum Fennoscandiae, Daniae et Baltiae. Sahlbergia. 9: 1-111.
- Skiles D.D. 1978. Notes on the Larval Habits of *Asemum caseyi* Linsley and *A. nitidum* LeConte (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). - The Pan-Pacific Entomologist. 54 (1): 14.
- Slosson A.T. 1894. List of insects taken in alpine region of Mt. Washington. - Entomological News, Philadelphia. 5 (1): 1-6.
- Slosson A.T. 1896. Additional list of insects taken in alpine region of Mt. Washington. - Entomological News, Philadelphia. 7 (9): 262-265.
- Smith J.B. 1900. Insects of New Jersey. A list of the species occurring in New Jersey, with notes on those of economic importance (Order Coleoptera). - In: Supplement of the 27th Annual Report of the State Board of Agriculture, Trenton (1899): 1-755, 328 figs, 2 maps.
- Smith J.B. 1910. A report of the insects of New Jersey (Order Coleoptera). - Annual Report of the New Jersey State Museum: 1-880, 340 figs.
- Stephens J.F. 1831. Illustrations of British Entomology or, a synopsis of indigenous insects; containing their generic and specific distinctions; with an account of their metamorphoses, times of appearance, localities, food, and economy,

M.A. Lazarev

- as far as practicable. *Mandibulata*. - Baldwin & Cradock. 4: 1-366.
- Stolbov V.A., Sergeeva E.V., Lomakin D.E. & Sheykin S.D. 2019. A check-list of longicorn beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of Tyumenskaya Oblast of Russia. - *Euroasian Entomological Journal*. 18 (3): 199-212.
- Švácha P. 1989. In: Švácha P. & Danilevsky M.L. 1989. *Cerambycoid larvae of Europe and Soviet Union (Coleoptera, Cerambycoidea)*. Part III. - *Acta Universitatis Carolinae*. 32 (1988) (1-2): 1-205.
- Švácha P. & Lawrence J.F. 2014. 2.4 Cerambycidae Latreille, 1802. Pp. 77-177. - In: Leschen R.A. B. & Beutel R.G. (eds). *Handbook of Zoology, Arthropoda: Insecta; Coleoptera, Beetles, Volume 3: Morphology and systematics (Phytophaga)*. Walter de Gruyter, Berlin/Boston: i-xii + 1-676, 465 figs.
- Swaine J.M. & Hopping R. 1928. *The Lepturini of America north of Mexico*. Part I. Canadian Department of Mines - *Bulletin of the National Museum of Canada, Ottawa (Biological series 14)*. 52: 1-97, 13 pls.
- Tanner V.M. 1927. A preliminary study of the genitalia of female Coleoptera. - *Transactions of the American Entomological Society, Philadelphia*. 53: 5-50, pls II-XV.
- Tanner V.M. 1928. *The Coleoptera of Zion National Park, Utah*. - *Annals of the Entomological Society of America, Columbus*. 21 (2): 269-297.
- Tamutis V., Tamutė B. & Ferenc R. 2011. A catalogue of Lithuanian beetles (Insecta, Coleoptera). - *ZooKeys*. 121: 1-494.
- Tavakilian, G. L. [Author] & Chevillotte, H. [Software] (2025) Titan: base de données internationales sur les Cerambycidae ou Longicornes. Version 30 novembre 2024. URL: <http://titan.gbif.fr/index.html> [Last accessed 12 May 2025].
- Thomas J.B. 1955. Notes on insects and other arthropods in red and white pine logging slash. - *The Canadian Entomologist*. 87 (8): 338-344.
- Thomson J. 1860-1861. *Essai d'une classification de la famille des cérambycides et matériaux pour servir à une monographie de cette famille*. Paris. 404 pp., 3 pls.
- Thomson J. 1864. *Systema Cerambycidarum ou exposé de tous les genres compris dans la famille des Cérambycides et familles limitrophes*. - *Mémoires de la Société Royale des Sciences de Liège*. 19: 1-540.
- Townes H. & Townes M. 1960. Ichneumon-flies of America, north of Mexico. 2. Subfamilies Ephialtinae, Xoridinae, Acaenitinae. - *Bulletin of the United States National Museum, Washington D.C.* 216 (2): i-vii + 1-676, 378 figs.
- Townsend C.H.T. 1889. Contribution to a list of the Coleoptera of the Lower peninsula of Michigan. - *Psyche, Cambridge, Massachusetts*. 5 (160-164): 231-235.
- Townsend C.H.T. 1895. On the Coleoptera of New Mexico and Arizona, including biologic and other notes. - *The Canadian Entomologist*. 27 (2): 39-51.
- Tozlu G., Rejzek M. & Özbek H. 2002. A contribution to the knowledge of Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) fauna of Turkey. - *Bioscosme Mésogéen*. 19 (1-2): 55-94.
- Trócoli S., Mercadé A., Oliete C. & Aibar R., 2023. Los Longicornios del Moianès (Barcelona, Catalunya) Les Longicornes du Moianès (Barcelona, Catalogne) (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Vesperidae). - *Revue de*

M.A. Lazarev

- l'Association Roussillonnaise d'Entomologie (R.A.R.E.). 32 (4): 237-247.
- Troukens W., Drumont A., Raemdonck H., Dekuijper C. & Dahan L. 2017. Nieuwe en interessante vondsten van boktorren (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) in de omgeving van Brussel. - Phegea. 45 (1): 13-18.
- Tsherepanov A.I. 1979. Longicorn Beetles of North Asia (Prioninae, Disteniinae, Lepturinae, Aseminae). Novosibirsk. 472 pp. [in Russian]
- Tyson W.H. 1966. Notes on Reared Cerambycidae (Coleoptera). - The Pan-Pacific Entomologist. 42 (3): 201-207.
- Ulke H. 1903. A list of the Beetles of the District of Columbia. - Proceedings of the United States National Museum, Washington D.C. 25 (1275): 1-57.
- Ulmen K., Newzella R., Hubweber L., Schmitt M., Klug T. & Ahrens D. 2010. Contribution to a catalogue of types preserved in the collection of Zoologisches Forschungsmuseum Alexander Koenig (ZFMK): Coleoptera: 1. Checklist of taxa. - Bonn zoological Bulletin. 58: 5-48.
- Villiers A. 1946. Coléoptères Cérambycides de l'Afrique du Nord. - Faune de l'Empire Français, ORSC Paris. 5: 1-152, 275 figs.
- Villiers A. 1978. Faune des coléoptères de France I. Cerambycidae. Encyclopédie Entomologique XLII. Paris: Editions Lechevalier. xxvii + 611 pp.
- Vincent R. 1998. Catalogue des Coléoptères de l'Île de France. Fascicule VII: Cerambycidae. - Supplément au Bulletin de Liaison de l'ACOREP. 32: 1-108.
- Vitali F. 2018. Atlas of the Insects of the Grand-Duchy of Luxembourg: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae. Ferrantia. Musée national d'histoire naturelle, Luxembourg. 79: 1-208, 342 figs.
- Vives E. 2000. Fauna Iberica, Vol 12: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae. Madrid: Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas. 724 pp.
- Vives E. 2001. Atlas fotográfico de los cerambycoides ibero-baleares. Argania editio, Barcelona. 287 pp.
- Vlasák J. & Vlasakova K. 2002. Records of Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) in Massachusetts with Notes on Larval Hosts. - The Coleopterists' Bulletin. 56 (2): 203-219.
- Voet J.E. 1806. Catalogus Systematicus Coleopterorum. Tomus II. La Haye, Bakhuyzen 2: 1-254, 50 pls.
- Volovnik S.V. 2024. New faunistic records of beetles (Coleoptera) from Southern Ukraine. - Munis Entomology & Zoology. 19 (1): 40-46.
- Wallin L. 1993. Uppsala University Zoological Museum Catalogue of type specimens. 4. Linnaean specimens. 2nd revised version. Uppsala (Uppsala University Zoological Museum). 127 pp.
- Warren J.C. 1899. [Coleoptera from Tioga County, Pennsylvania]. - Entomological News, Philadelphia. 10 (10): 295-296.
- Warzee N. & Drumont A. 2004. Contribution à l'étude des Longicornes de l'Ardenne avec la découverte d'une nouvelle espèce pour la Belgique : *Acanthocinus griseus* (Fabricius) (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae). - Lambillionea. 104 (1) 1: 45-57.
- Wenzel H.W. 1905. Feldman Collection Social. March 11, 1905. [Rhagium lineatum]. - Entomological News, Philadelphia. 16: 159.
- Westwood J.O. 1839. Synopsis of the genera of British Insects. In An introduction to the

M.A. Lazarev

- modern classification of insects; founded on the natural habits and corresponding organisation of the different families. London, Longman. 1: 1-462.
- Wickham H.F. 1897a. The Coleoptera of Canada XXII. The Cerambycidae of Ontario and Quebec. - The Canadian Entomologist. 29 (4): 81-88.
- Wickham H.F. 1897b. The Coleoptera of Canada. XXV. The Cerambycidae of Ontario and Quebec. - The Canadian Entomologist. 29 (7): 169-173.
- Wilson D.A. 1971. Notes and observations on Lepturini in New England (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). - The Coleopterists' Bulletin. 25 (2): 59-62.
- Winkler A. 1929. Cerambycidae. - In: Catalogus Coleopterorum regionis palaearticae. Wien, Winkler et Wagner.: 1135-1226.
- Wolcott A.B. & Montgomery B.E. 1933. An ecological study of the coleopterous fauna of a tamarack swamp. - American Midland Naturalist. 14 (2): 113-169.
- Woodruff L.B. 1917. In Proceedings of the New York Entomological Society. Meeting of November 7. - Journal of the New York Entomological Society. 25 (1): 85-86.
- Yalçın M., Akcay C., Taşçioğlu C., Yüksel B. & Özbayram A.K. 2020. Damage severity of wood-destroying insects according to the Bevan damage classification system in log depots of Northwest Turkey. - Scientific Reports. 10 (13705): 1-12.
- Zamoroka A.M. 2022. The longhorn beetles (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) of Ukraine: Results of two centuries of research. - Biosystems Diversity. 30 (1): 46-73.
- Zaragoza-Caballero S. & Pérez-Hernández C.X. 2017. An annotated catalogue of the Coleoptera types deposited in the National Insect Collection (CNIN) of the National Autonomous University of Mexico. - Zootaxa. 4288 (1): 1-128.
- Żurawlew P. & Melke A. 2018. The longhorn beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) of Pleszew District (Wielkopolska-Kujawy Lowland). - Przegląd Przyrodniczy. 29 (2): 80-97.

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